

Methods for Health studies

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Methods	Analysis
<i>Health outcome: Dental professionals</i>			
Duplinsky 2012, [USA]; JAP ¹	Cohort with control group	Health status: insurance utilisation data. Authors given permission by participants to access pharmacy claims data, medical claims data, and biographical data. A pharmaceutical benefits manager (PBM) and third-party administrator (TPA) contacted to obtain data. Population data base developed by PBM using social security number identifier. Data used in this study reflect a combination of census information, raw prescription claims, National Drug Code (NDC) information, authors' own drug categories, dentist specialty information and miscellaneous code and description tables e.g. gender description and age groups tables. Data transmitted to authors for analysis with social security number identifier modified by altering algorithm, protecting anonymity.	Hypothesis medication usage Dentists>Controls: standard chi-squared, employing relative risk ratio. Hypothesis with increasing age increasing medication usage, with dentist>controls: Jonckheere's Z used. Hypothesis statistically significant differences Dentists vs Controls at specific age groupings: Chi-square (d) test with Yates correction for continuity.
Heggland 2011, [Norway]; JAP ²	Retrospective cohort study (records review)	Obtained lists of current/previous employees in public dental healthcare system from all 19 counties in Norway except Rogaland. Employees registered from archive establishment (all prior to 1967) until data collection (2007/2008) included. Relevant data: name, address, national identification number, occupation, place of work, education level, time period employed or member of trade union, and graduation year for dentists. From Medical Birth Registry of Norway (MBRN): child/parent demographic information, complications/interventions during pregnancy and delivery, maternal health before/ during pregnancy and condition of newborn, delivery year, diagnoses, prenatal death, birth weight, gestational age, gender, plurality, maternal age, and parity. Infants delivered to female dental personnel during 1967–2006=exposed group; deliveries to all other females=unexposed/control group. Categories congenital malformations: all congenital malformations registered in the MBRN, major congenital malformations (as defined by the MBRN), malformations of the central nervous system (anencephaly, spina bifida, encephalocele, and hydrocephalus), dysplasia of the hip, clubfoot, and malformations of the heart and great vessels. Other adverse pregnancy outcomes: low birth weight (<2500 grams), preterm delivery (<37 weeks gestational age), small for gestational age (SGA, weight below the 10th percentile for actual gestational age in Norwegian newborns), gender distribution (higher proportion of boys), multiple births, stillbirth (death prior to or during	Negative binomial regression models with log link: excess risks of adverse pregnancy outcomes for dental personnel compared vs control group. Poisson regression used when standard method could not be performed due to collinearity. Adjusted for confounders: parity (1, 2, ≥3), year of delivery, maternal age, maternal education. Relative risks (RR) with 95% CI estimated with births clustered by mother. For most frequent congenital malformations and other adverse pregnancy outcomes, estimated time trend and tested for delivery year by occupation interaction and stratified by 10-year periods. Analyses performed using all dental personnel and sub-analyses using only dental personnel with known employment prior to delivery.

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		delivery) and prenatal death (stillbirth or death during the first month of life).	
Heratizadeh 2018, [Germany, Switzerland, Austria]; JAP ³	Case control	Patch tests performed and read according to German Contact Dermatitis Research Group (DKG) and the Information Network of Departments of Dermatology (IVDK) guidelines. For data analysis, patch test reactions on day (D) 3 selected. When reading performed on Day 4 instead of Day 3, Day 4 reading chosen.	Reaction prevalences standardised for age and sex. Statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) of differences in sensitisation frequencies determined by use of non-overlapping 95% CIs of reaction prevalences. Differences in proportions of population characteristics between study and control group: χ^2 -test.
Hilt 2009, [Norway]; JAP ⁴	Cross sectional with control group	Primary questionnaire: comprised a Norwegian version of the standardised European questionnaire called "Euroquest", designed to monitor cognitive symptoms in subjects exposed to neurotoxic substances. Used part of the questionnaire related to mood, memory, concentration, sleep disturbances, neurological symptoms, psychosomatic symptoms, and fatigue. Second questionnaire related to work career and working conditions while working in the dental health care system. Urine mercury levels: Information for all dental assistants held at National Institute of Occupational Health. Samples analysed by cold vapour flameless atomic absorption spectrophotometry. Control group completed the primary questionnaire in the same way as the dental assistants.	Differences between dental assistants and controls in scores for each symptom group: general linear modelling controlling for age and educational level. 5% level statistical significance, two-sided p values.
Hilt, 2011, [Norway]; JAP ⁵	Cross sectional with control group	As above	Outcome variables presented as mean scores for each symptom group, sum of symptom scores, and prevalence subjects reporting >3 symptoms "often"/more frequently stratified by sex and 10-year age groups. Statistical significance assessed via chi square test and student's t -test.
Jones, 2007, [New Zealand]; JAP ⁶	Cross sectional with control group	Data collection: mostly in participants' own homes. Preliminary questionnaire: physical injuries, health, work history, environmental influences health. Reproductive health: fertility, childbirth, infants' health. Environmental influences: toxins and chemicals relating to 1 year period prior to survey. Mercury exposed group asked open-ended questions regarding memory of mercury-poisoning episode and work history. Neurobehavioral tests: adapted for middle-aged NZ women, included: CVLT (adult research version; cognitive skills), Rey 15-item test (memory), SDMT (executive function), and POMS bipolar form (mood).	General health: comparisons between groups - Chi-squared test. Illness symptoms analysed separately by time. Thyroid problems between groups (Mann-Whitney U test). Reproductive health: descriptive statistics and Pearson's Correlation coefficient. Neurobehavioral test battery: descriptive statistics, two-tailed t -tests.
Lindbohm, 2007, [Finland]; JAP ⁷	Retrospective/cross-sectional with control	Pregnancy/birth data: Women identified through trade union information. Information on births in the years 1992–8 obtained from the Finnish Medical Birth Register. Data on miscarriages came from the Hospital Care Register of the National Research and Development Centre for Welfare and Health (Helsinki, Finland), and collected nationally from the hospitals on	Exposure assessment: an occupational hygienist assessed participants' exposure to acrylate compounds, disinfectants and solvents. Exposure to TEGDMA determined by the number of removed composite resin restorations per week. Exposure to mercury amalgam classified by number of amalgam fillings made and removed per week. Cumulative

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		patients who were treated in the outpatient units of the hospitals and not included in the Hospital Care Register. The first eligible pregnancy of a woman during the study period was selected for study. Data on malformations obtained from Finnish Register of Congenital Malformations.	exposure to mercury amalgam assessed by years of exposure before pregnancy. Statistical analysis: Odds ratios (ORs) and confidence intervals (CIs) were estimated using conditional logistic regression. Confounders included in final models: maternal and paternal confounders - employment, year of beginning of pregnancy, number of amalgam fillings (in model on mercury amalgam), exposure to solvents and x radiation adjusted in in the multivariate analyses on other chemical agents. Age adjusted by adding a centred age variable to the conditional logistic model.
Naimi-Akbar, 2012, [Sweden]; JAP ⁸	Retrospective cohort with control	Cognitive function exam: used during military enlistment until 1997 (known as enlistment battery 67 and enlistment battery 80). Four tests: two linguistic understanding, one ability to use oral/written language, one spatial recognition, one technical comprehension.	Test scores transformed on a normalised standard scale of nine units, with an average of five. Used standardised scores ranging from 1–9 for each test. Linear regression: compared mean scores for four test components between cohorts. Adjusted for father’s educational level, mother’s age at birth, older siblings, and birth decade. Maternal exposure prior to birth: years between first census dentist or dental nurse registered and time of delivery. P-values <0.05 and confidence intervals not including 0 considered statistically significant.
Naimi-Akbar 2014, [Sweden]; JAP ⁹	Retrospective cohort with control	Data collected using Swedish registers. Two cohorts of male offspring potentially exposed to elemental mercury due to mother’s occupation matched with two comparison cohorts.	Cox proportional hazard models: all outcomes. Separate models for 3 categories of mortality and separate models for calendar periods 1960S, 1970s, 1980S. Analysis adjusted for maternal age and father’s education level. Subjects clustered by mothers. Interaction of mortality risk over 3 decades examined. Schoenfeld residuals test: tested proportional hazard assumption.
Thygesen 2010, [Finland]; JAP ¹⁰	Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study	Exposure: Used information from Supplementary Pension Fund Register (ATP) on the annual percentage of employment for all years, to construct a first date of employment and a date of termination of employment. A proxy measure for excess cumulative mercury exposure among dental personnel compared with the general population was calculated as the weighted amount of occupational mercury exposure during their working career multiplied by the annual percentage of employment. The weights were based on urine samples from Norwegian dental personnel collected since the late 1950s. Outcome: Hospital admissions due to neurological disease except eye and ear disease (ICD-8, 320e359; ICD-10, G00-G99), Parkinson’s Disease (ICD-8, 342.9; ICD-10, G20) and renal disease except nephritis and obstructive uropathy (ICD-8, 580e584 and 590e593; ICD-10, N00eN08 and N14eN29). Primary and secondary diagnoses in the analyses were included	Performed two types of analyses for each health outcome: (1) a between-group analysis where the hospital admission rates for dentists and dental assistants were compared with control groups and (2) a within-group analysis where dentists and dental assistants with employment during periods with high mercury exposure were compared with dentists and dental assistants employed during periods with less mercury exposure. In the between-group analysis, relative rates among dentists and dental assistants were compared with control groups to examine whether they were higher during periods with occupational mercury exposure compared with periods with no excess occupational mercury exposure. In the within-group analyses, the effect of cumulative weighted exposure among dental assistants and dentists on each health outcome was evaluated.

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		and the date of admission was used as date of diagnosis - Danish National Patient Register.	
Health outcome: Patients			
Adams, 2008, [USA]; JAP ¹¹	Case control	Sample collection and Hg determination: First-cut baby hair samples collected from families (historical samples stored for years in e.g. baby books). Prior to digestion, hair samples treated with acetone to minimise contamination. Hair sample aliquots (approximately 5 mg) digested using high-purity acids and oxidants in oven heated to 90C. Acidified samples containing Hg(II) introduced into cold vapor atomic fluorescence spectrometry (CVAFS) instrument and subjected to reducing agent resulting in Hg(0) vapour formation. Vapour transferred to Hg-specific atomic fluorescence detector with a stream of argon gas. Numerous quality controls were processed with sample batches to continuously monitor analytical performance. Controls included method blanks to monitor the analytical background from the reagents and procedure, Hg-fortified method controls to assess analyte recovery in the absence of sample matrix, certified reference materials to monitor accuracy, and duplicate preparations and analyses to assess sample preparation and analysis precision. Quality control data consistent with data collected by lab in support of the 1999–2000 National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES). Medical history: parents completed medical history form to determine child's Hg exposure. Medical history included child's vaccination record, manufacturer's name, and lot number. Autism families completed standardised questionnaire of autism severity, the Autism Treatment Evaluation Checklist (ATEC) retrospectively for their child at 3 years.	Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA) used to analyse 20 hair samples at MIT Nuclear Reactor Lab (MIT-NRL) as verification of CVAFS. Neutron irradiation performed using one pneumatic tube (1PH1), which had a high-quality thermal neutron flux of $8 \times 10^{12} \text{ n cm}^{-2} \text{ s}$, at the 5 MITR-II. Each hair sample irradiated in original poly vial and enclosed in another poly bag to avoid surface contamination. Flux standard and control standard used: Montana soil (NIST SRM-2710) and IAEA human hair (IAEA SRM-086), respectively. After irradiation, samples allowed to decay for several days and counted on high purity germanium (HPGe) detectors for 2 days. Gamma spectrum analysis performed with Canberra's Genie-2000 software. Hg+ other trace elements also analysed. Medical histories for children compared for 2 groups using a 2-sided t-test assuming equal variance. Due to non-normal distributions of Hg in baby hair, logistic regression analysis conducted to compare two groups. p-values <0.05 were considered statistically significant.
Ahlgren, 2014, [USA]; JAP ¹²	Case control	Questionnaire/medical history: all oral lichen lesions (OLL) and dermatitis patients (DP) completed questions on general and oral health, current medication and skin problems. Remaining DP group controls (n=44) answered oral health questions. Clinical oral examination: dental filling surfaces and oral mucosal lesions. Biopsies of lesions in OLL group. Epicutaneous tests: lichen series (66 substances used in dentistry/locally in oral cavity) developed and tested on patient's upper back. Test preparations in petrolatum (pet): 30 mg applied. Liquid test preparations: 25 µl applied using micropipette. Patches removed by patient after 48 hours, read by dermatologist on days 3 & 7. Control patients: tested with supplemented European baseline series and other substances depending on reasons for	Significance level p<0.05. Pearson's chi-square test and Fisher's exact test evaluated differences between groups. T test to compare amalgam and composite surfaces between OLL/DP groups.

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		referral. DP group: also tested with 34 of 66 substances included in lichen series tested on OLL patients. OLL patients with doubtful reactions to mercury 0.5 % (w/w) pet on day 3 retested with mercury 1.6 % (w/w) Softisan.	
New England Children's Amalgam Trial			
Bellinger, 2006, [USA]; JAP ¹³	RCT	Neurological outcomes: Full-scale IQ (WISC-III), Wechsler Individual Achievement Test, Behavioural Assessment System for Children. Administered: baseline, 3 & 5 years. Neuropsychological tests administered baseline and years 1, 2 and 4: Wide Range Assessment of Visual Motor Ability, the Wide Range Assessment of Memory and Learning, the Stroop Color-Word Interference Test, the Wisconsin Card Sorting Test, the Trail-Making Test, a verbal cancellation task, tests of verbal fluency, finger tapping, and reaction time (auditory memory, visual-motor integration, attention, emotional state) by trained assessors. Hair/Urinary Hg: annual timed overnight urine samples.	Comparisons between treatment groups - exposure to dental materials and urinary Hg: Wilcoxon rank-sum tests. Incidence adverse events: Fisher exact test. 5-year change in IQ and 4-year change in general memory index and visuomotor composite scores: Intention-to-treat analyses, analysis of covariance used to model - as a function of assigned treatment group, adjusting for baseline score and randomization stratum. Adjustments made for baseline covariates, including age, sex, socioeconomic status, hair mercury concentration, and blood lead level. Hair mercury included to control for dietary sources of mercury. Repeated measures model with both 3-year/5-year change in IQ fit with/without interaction between treatment group and year. Further sensitivity analyses included adjustment for time between baseline/ follow-up, an adjustment for potential inter-examiner differences, an as-treated analysis, and dose-response model (using amalgam exposure measured in surface years of amalgam fillings). Albumin: ANOVA model year-5 creatinine-corrected albumin as a function of assigned treatment group, adjusting for randomisation stratum. In secondary analyses, adjustments were made for baseline covariates but also included urine collection type (overnight or spot), urinary creatinine concentration, lean body mass, and sample storage time. Controlled for collection type (i.e., time) and creatinine concentration to take into account urinary flow rate. A log transformation was used because albumin was log-normally distributed. In addition, a repeated-measures model with both 3-year and 5-year albumin was fit with and without the interaction between treatment group and year. All statistical tests were 2-sided, performed at an alpha level of .05.
Barregard, 2008, [USA], JAP ¹⁴	RCT	Dental amalgam/Hg exposure: key measure of mercury burden: mercury in urine, corrected for creatinine (U-Hg in micrograms per gram creatinine). Hair/blood Hg measured. Renal markers: at baseline and in annual follow-up, the level of γ -GT was determined as well as a dip-stick test of proteinuria. At 3 and 5 years, added assays of albumin, A1M, and NAG, to	Data analysis controlled for urine storage time. Data analyses were performed based on renal markers as continuous as well as categorical variables. For albumin, 30 mg/g creatinine was used as the cutoff for microalbuminuria (MA). For urinary A1M, NAG, and γ -GT, there were no general reference limits in children. Therefore, the 95th percentiles

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		<p>assess possible mild renal effects. γ-GT was measured in Clinical Laboratory of the Rochester General Hospital (Rochester, NY, USA) using the Dimension system GGT Flex reagent cartridge from Dade Behring. Urinary albumin, A1M, and NAG determined at the Sahlgrenska University Hospital. Urinary creatinine was determined at the Swedish and the Rochester laboratories by the photometric Jaffe method (detection limit 0.1 g/L).</p>	<p>were used in the composite group for years 1–5 (γ-GT), year 5 (A1M with ELISA), or years 3–5 (the other markers). When the renal markers were analysed as continuous variables, levels were log-transformed. Three outcome times were considered: a) year 1 for γ-GT (first visit after placement of dental fillings), b) years 3–5 for all markers except A1M with ELISA, and c) year 5 (end of the trial) for all markers. Three predictors were used for each outcome: treatment group, number of amalgam and composite fillings (two separate variables), and U-Hg level (years 3–5 only). Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) (for the continuous outcomes) was used and logistic regression (for the categorial outcomes) for all three predictors. All models controlled for randomisation stratum, age, sex, race (non-Hispanic white, non-Hispanic black, Hispanic, other), socioeconomic status, baseline hair mercury level, baseline blood lead level (BPb), lean body mass, type of specimen (overnight vs. spot daytime urine sample), urinary creatinine concentration (as a surrogate for urinary flow rate), storage time, and baseline γ-GT (for γ-GT models only). In the models with U-Hg as predictor, a term for an interaction between BPb and U-Hg was tested.</p>
Bellinger 2007, [Dose effect analysis] [USA]: JAP ¹⁵	RCT (secondary analysis)	<p>Surface-years of amalgam exposure: dental clinic records for data regarding dates of amalgam placement, number of tooth surfaces, involved in the restoration, and the timing of the loss of primary teeth containing amalgam restorations. Urinary mercury excretion: urine samples collected and tested annually for elemental mercury using CVAA (cold vapour atomic absorption) (see analysis for reporting detail). Values were expressed as micrograms of mercury per gram of Cr. Annual neuropsychological evaluations: primary outcome was a change on the Full-Scale IQ score on the WIS-III between baseline and at 5 yrs after study enrolment; secondary outcomes were the scores on the GMI from the Wide Range Assessment and Learning and the VMC from the Wide Range Assessment of Visual Motor Abilities. These secondary outcomes were assessed for the last time at 4 years after study enrolment.</p>	<p>Surface-years of amalgam exposure: calculated number of amalgam surfaces weighted by number of years present in mouth. Changes in WISC-III Full Scale IQ score in relation to amalgam exposure, evaluated using surface-years of amalgam between baseline and 5 years follow-up. Surface-years of amalgam between baseline and 4 years follow-up evaluation was used to assess changes in GMI and VMC scores in relation to amalgam exposure. Urinary mercury excretion: to analyse the changes in WISC-III Full Scale IQ score in relation to urinary mercury excretion, the mean of available urinary mercury excretions was used at the 3, 4 and 5 years follow-up. ANCOVA to evaluate the associations between the two continuously distributed indexes of mercury dose and the change in scores for the three neuropsychological test. Adjustments made for: test score, randomisation stratum, age, sex, family socioeconomic status, hair mercury concentration and blood lead level. Likelihood of nonlinearity in the associations assessed by constructing histograms of test scores and by stratifying subjects by surface-years of amalgam or by urinary mercury excretion.</p>
Bellinger 2007, [Dental]	RCT	<p>Neuropsychological assessment: At baseline, before randomisation and the receipt of any dental treatments. Three-hour neuropsychological test</p>	<p>Intention to treat analysis: analysis of covariance to compare amalgam and composite groups in terms of the changes, over 5 years, in scores</p>

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amalgam restorations, neuropsychological function] [USA]; JAP ¹⁶		sessions. Session 1: WISC-III and Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT). Administered again at 3 and 5 years after baseline. Session 2: domain-focused tests: WRAML, WRAVMA, Trail-Making Test, finger tapping, ordered and unordered verbal cancellation, Controlled Oral Word Association Test, simple visual reaction time, Stroop Color-World Interference Test, Wisconsin Card Sorting Test. Administered again at 1,2, 4 years after baseline. 14 testers at Boston/Cambridge site and 5 at Farmington site.	on the WISC-III and WIAT and the changes, over 4 years, in scores on the domain-focused tests. Adjustments made for baseline covariates: test score, randomisation stratum, age, sex, socioeconomic status, hair mercury, and blood lead level. Children's neuropsychological test scores in relation to surface-years of amalgam (number of amalgam surfaces weighted/number of years present) and mean U-Hg concentration (WISC-II and WIAT evaluated against U-Hg years 3, 4, and 5; other tests in relation to U-Hg at years 3 and 4): tested using analysis of covariance. Adjusted for same baseline covariates in intention to-treat analyses. Analyses conducted using Kolmogorov-Smirnov test.
Bellinger 2008, [[Psychosocial]] [USA]; JAP ¹⁷	RCT	Dental amalgam/Hg exposure: primary index of a child's exposure was treatment group assignment. Two secondary indices were also considered. (i) surface-years of amalgam, calculated from a child's dental records, prospectively assembled over the course of the trial. (ii) urinary mercury excretion. Urine samples were collected annually and analysed for elemental mercury by cold vapour atomic absorption. Values were expressed as µg mercury/gram creatinine (µg/g Cr). In analyses, the mean urinary mercury concentration in samples collected at 3, 4, and 5 years of follow-up were used. Samples with a mercury concentration below the detection limit were assigned a value of 0.45/√2. The primary psychosocial outcomes were scores on the Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL), completed by a parent at baseline prior to dental treatment and 5 years later at the completion of the trial. Yielded four global T-scores: Competence, Internalizing Behavior Problems, Externalizing Behavior Problems, and Total Problem Behaviors. Secondary outcomes were children's self-reports at the five-year evaluation on the Behavior Assessment System for Children (BASC-SR).	Associations between children's CBCL change scores and treatment group using analyses of covariance. The BASC-SR analyses evaluated treatment group differences at 5 years. Analysis of covariance models were used, adjusted for the same covariates used in the CBCL analyses; adjusted for baseline score, age, gender, race, socio-economic status, primary caregiver's marital status, birth weight, maternal exposure during pregnancy to tobacco, alcohol, and drugs, family stress, baseline child Full-Scale IQ, and randomisation stratum (i.e., the four strata defined by geographic location and number of teeth with caries at baseline); Urine samples were analysed for elemental mercury by cold vapour atomic absorption. Values were expressed as µg mercury/gram creatinine (µg/g Cr).
Maserejian 2012, [dental composites, amalgam, physical health] [USA]; JAP ¹⁸	RCT (secondary analysis)	NECAT data collectors measured height, weight and body fat percentage annually. Height: tape measured/ruler. Weight and body fat percentage: bio-impedance scale. Menarche status: reported annually (no/yes. If yes, month+ year). BMI (kg/m ²) and BMI-for-age z-score: Centers for Disease Control (CDC) data files (overweight/obese=BMI-for-age z-scores: ≥ 85th percentile). Accelerated growth in height: height velocity=change in height between consecutive annual measurements.	Exposure: Intention-to-treat randomised group analysis and observational treatment-level analyses. Generalised Linear Model: age-adjusted growth measures. Linear mixed-effects models and repeated measures of growth outcomes and subject-specific intercepts and age-specific slopes. Adjusted models for: randomisation stratum, age, baseline anthropometric measure, severity dental disease. Multivariable models adjusted for age, body fat percentage, birth weight, maternal education, household income, race/ethnicity, randomisation stratum. Final models retained age, birth weight, and income. Statistical significance: alpha = 0.05.

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Maserejian 2012, [Neuro] [USA]; JAP ¹⁹	RCT	Neuropsychological testing - psychologist trained/supervised interviewer administered at baseline and 2 sessions during 5- year follow-up. Baseline, years 3 and 5: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children-Third Edition (WISC-III), Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT). Baseline and years 1, 2 & 4: battery domain focused tests: Wide Range Assessment of Memory and Learning (WRAML), Wide Range Test of Visual-Motor Ability (WRAVMA), Trail-Making Test (TMT), ordered/unordered verbal cancellation task, category fluency, Controlled Oral Word Association Test (COWAT) (letter fluency, Standard Reaction Timer (SRT), Stroop Colour-Word Interference Test and the Wisconsin Card Sorting Test (WCST).	Multivariate generalised linear regression models: association exposure measures with neuropsychological test scores. Covariates: age, sex, SES, geographic site, baseline blood lead level. Effect modification by age, sex, gum chewing toothbrushing frequency investigated. MANOVA: linear combination tests executive functioning. Sensitivity analyses: total surface-years and number of extant filled surfaces.
Maserejian 2012, [Dental composite restorations and psychosocial function] [USA]; JAP ²⁰	RCT	Psychosocial assessments: two validated instruments at baseline and follow-up: (1) Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL) parent-report; (2) Behavior Assessment for Children Self-Report (BASC-SR). Examiners trained/certified by supervising psychologist.	Multivariable generalised linear regression models: beta-estimates for exposure measures. Confounders: age, gender, race/ethnicity, socioeconomic status, geographic site, primary caregiver's marital status, blood lead level, and any maternal self-reported exposure during pregnancy to alcohol or illicit substances, age and gender. Significance level $\alpha = 0.05$.
Maserejian 2014, [Dental sealants and flowable composite restorations] [USA]; JAP ²¹	RCT	Psychosocial assessments: administered baseline and follow up by examiners trained/certified by supervising psychologist. Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL) (parent-report) and Behavior Assessment for Children Self-Report (BASC-SR) (self-report). Primary outcome: BASC-SR on four global scales (Total emotional symptoms index, clinical maladjustment, school maladjustment, personal adjustment). Secondary behavioural outcomes: BASC-SR subscale scores, CBCL change scores and percentage of children with at-risk/clinically significant scores. Neuropsychological assessments: battery of tests on executive functioning, intelligence, memory, visual-spatial skills, verbal fluency, and problem-solving. Outcomes: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children-Third Edition (WISC-III), and factors of verbal comprehension, perceptual organisation, freedom from distractibility, processing speed, reading and math scores and executive function tests: Trail-Making Test, Letter Fluency subtest of verbal fluency, Stroop Colour-Word Interference Test, and Wisconsin Card Sorting Test. Physical health: height, weight, body fat percentage.	Associations examined: multivariable models adjusting for sociodemographic/dental variables. Cofounders: age, sex, race/ethnicity, household income, socioeconomic status, primary care giver's marital status, geographic study region, blood lead level, fruit/vegetable intake, maternal alcohol/tobacco/drug exposure during pregnancy, composite restorations. Variables retained if model associated with outcome at $p < 0.02$.
Maserejian 2014, [Dental sealants and composite	RCT	Immune function: Blood samples baseline and time-points after initial dental treatment: 5–7 days, 6 months, 12 months, 18 months, and 5 years. Parameters assessed: (i) white blood cell (WBC) enumeration; (ii) T-cell responsiveness; (iii) B-cell responsiveness; and (iv) neutrophil and monocyte	Multivariable linear mixed effects models with repeated measures of immune function at 6 months, 12 months, 18 months, and 5 years follow-up: estimate the association between exposure to resin composites and immune function changes from baseline values. All

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restorations] [USA]; JAP ²²		responsiveness. Total WBC enumeration using Wright's stain and hemocytometer. Distribution of neutrophils, monocytes, T-cells, B-cells, natural killer cells, and cluster of differentiation (CD) subtypes CD4 and CD8: flow cytometry using IMK and Simultest kit. Functional analysis of T-cells after mitogenic activation: 1) analysis of activation markers, 2) cell cycle distribution. T-cells were incubated with phytohemagglutinin (PHA) (5 µg/mL) for 24 hours to assess expression of activation markers; CD69 +CD25 expression: immunofluorescence using flow cytometry. Cell cycle distribution assessed after 72 hours' incubation in presence of PHA. B-cell activation monitored by analysing expression of CD69 and increased expression CD23 after stimulation with pokeweed mitogen (PWM) (10 µg/mL). Functional status of neutrophils and monocytes: monitoring oxidative burst in response to stimulation with phorbol myristate acetate (PMA) (0.5 µg/mL). Fluorescent probes dihydroethidium and dihydrorhodamine used to assess superoxide and hydrogen peroxide (H2O2) generation; fluorescence: flow cytometry 30 minutes after cell activation.	multivariable models adjusted for baseline age, blood lead level, asthma, allergy, and study site.
Shenker 2008, [USA]; JAP ²³	RCT (secondary analysis)	Total urinary Hg (years 3-5), hair Hg, Blood lead measured. Immunological outcomes: Heparinized blood: white blood cell enumeration (WBC) via Wirght's stain and hemocytometer, assessment of T- and B-cell responsiveness and analysis of neutrophil and monocyte responsiveness. Distribution of neutrophils, monocytes, T cells, B cells, NK cells as well as CD4 and CD8 subtypes was determined by flow cytometry using the IMK+ Simultest kit (Becton Dickinson). Functional analysis of T cells following mitogenic activation employed two approaches: analysis of activation and cell cycle distribution. T-cells incubated with phytohemagglutinin [(PHA); 5 µg/ml] for 24 hrs to assess expression of activation markers; CD69 and CD25 expression was determined by immunofluorescence using flow cytometry. Cell cycle distribution was assessed after 72hour incubation in the presence of PHA. B cell activation was monitored by analysing expression of CD69 and increased expression of CD23 following stimulation with pokeweed mitogen [(PWM); 10 µg/ml]. Functional status neutrophils and monocytes: monitoring phorbol myristate acetate (PMA); 0.5 µg/ml]-induced oxidative burst.	Primary analysis: comparison immune function markers by treatment assignment. Time trends calculated/treatment group. ANCOVA models: change over time/outcome. Included: y main effects, adjusted for baseline corresponding immune function measurement, age, gender, SES, hair Hg, and blood Pb. Secondary analysis: compared immune outcomes by urinary-Hg excretion at year 5 with ANCOVA, restricted to participants with both immune function measures and U-Hg measures at year 5 (n=20 amalgam group, n=23 composite group). All statistical tests were 2-sided, performed at an alpha 0.05.
Bjorkman 2018, [Norway]; JAP ²⁴	Prospective longitudinal	Data on number of teeth and number of teeth with amalgam fillings, personal characteristics, retrieved from questionnaire; self-reported data;	Only singleton births were included in the analyses. Crude and adjusted ORs were calculated using logistic regression analysis. To explore

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		timeframe - 1999 to 2008. Maternal age, birth weight, length of gestation at delivery, parity and perinatal death were retrieved from the Medical Birth Registry of Norway (MBRN).	changes over time in the exposure to dental amalgam in the cohort, the mean number of teeth filled with amalgam was calculated by year of inclusion in the cohort. Sensitivity analyses carried out. Adjustment for potential confounders (mothers' age, education, body mass index, parity, smoking during pregnancy, alcohol consumption during pregnancy).
Bergen Amalgam Trial			
Bjorkman 2020, [Norway]; JAP ²⁵	Prospective longitudinal with pre-post and control	General Health Complaints index (GHC index) at 12-month follow-up after completed amalgam removal.	Continuous variables were presented as mean values with standard deviation (SD) and in box-plots indicating median, percentiles, max and min values. 95% confidence intervals for mean values were presented when appropriate. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies. Statistical methods: the statistical model was built upon the pre-defined null-hypothesis that there were no differences between the Amalgam cohort and the MUPS cohort with respect to the change scores for the primary outcome variable. Statistical testing of potential differences between the groups was performed by analysis of variance complemented by an adjustment for covariates (baseline value of the primary change score, age, gender and education). Predictors of change of the primary outcome measure at follow-up were subject to multivariate analysis including the potential effect modifier. The comparison between treatment group and comparison group included only patients who responded to the follow-up questionnaire (per-protocol analysis). When appropriate, p-values were adjusted for multiple comparisons using the Bonferroni correction.
Bjorkman 2023, [Norway]; JAP ²⁶	Prospective longitudinal	Concentration of trace elements in serum (mercury, silver, and selenium). Blood samples: collected using serum tubes (BD Vacutainer SST II Plus Advance). Concentration of I-Hg was estimated by calculating the difference between the concentration of total mercury and the concentration of MeHg. Self-reported questionnaires: General Health Complaints (GHC) index was the sum score calculated from numeric rating scales of 12 items (musculoskeletal complaints, gastrointestinal complaints, cardiovascular complaints, skin problems, complaints related to eyes/sight, complaints related to ears/hearing/nose/throat, tiredness, dizziness, headaches, memory problems, difficulty concentrating, and anxiety/depression).	Trace element data - Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test; Mann Whitney U-test or Kruskal Wallis Test; Kendall's tau <i>b</i> was used. GHC index - logistic regression; paired sample t-test; linear mixed models were used to analyse changes over time from baseline (Q1) to the first (Q2) and second follow-up (Q3) in relation to concentration of I-Hg in serum. Within-group and between-group effect sizes (Cohen's <i>d</i>); the regression coefficients from analysis by linear mixed models of z-transformed data.
Sinha 2024, [Norway]; JAP ²⁷	Prospective cohort (with control groups)	Baseline questionnaire (Q1) was sent to all three cohorts. Amalgam cohort: restorations removed and follow-up questionnaire (Q2) sent by mail 1 year after removal of the last restoration. Follow-up questionnaire (Q3) sent 5	Data analysed by linear mixed models. When residuals skewed, Friedman's test used to calculate significance for change over time within group. Effect size estimated by calculating 'standardised response

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Methods	Analysis
		years after restorations (4 years after Q2); Medically unexplained physical symptoms (MUPS) cohort and healthy cohort: Q2 was sent 2 years after the completion of Q1. Q3 sent 4 years after completion of Q2. Self-reported health symptoms questionnaires: 1) General Health Complaints (GHC)-index at 12-month follow-up after amalgam removal was completed. The GHC-index is the sum score of 12 items, scored by numeric rating scales from 0 (no symptoms) to 10 (worst imaginable symptoms). Local (intraoral and extra oral) complaints were included for the Amalgam cohort and for the Healthy cohort. 2) The Munich Amalgam Scale was included in the questionnaires distributed to the Amalgam cohort The scale included 50 items and each item was scored 0 (not at all), 1 (a little), 2 (quite a lot), or 3 (very much).	mean' (SRM) by dividing mean change score by standard deviation of change score. Values of 0.20 represent a small response, values of 0.50 represent a medium response, and values of 0.80 represent a large response. P-values<0.05 statistically significant.
Bjorkman 2012, [Norway]; JAP ²⁸	Prospective longitudinal with pre-post and control	Serum samples of patients collected at the pre-treatment examination by clinicians before amalgam removal (baseline), and 3 and 12 months after the removal was finished. All serum samples were stored at -80 °C before analysis. Serum samples of blood donors (comparison group): retrieved from an existing biobank.	Cytokines in serum: analysed using Luminex 100 system. A multiplex bead kit was used including four panels: an "inflammatory panel", a "Th1/Th2 panel", a "cytokine panel", and a "chemokine panel". All samples analysed as single samples and in the same assay. One single plate was used to minimize analytical variability. A minimum of 100 beads (n ≥ 100) per analyte (CV% is often below 10) were read and response data from the analyses were reduced to the median value before further statistical analysis. Anti-nuclear antibodies (ANA): analysed by a bead-based multiplex immunoassay was performed. It provided semi-quantitative antibody levels against the following auto-antigens: Ro60 (SS-A), Ro52 (SS-A), La48 (SS-B), Jo1, Sm, RNP, Scl-70, Ribosomal P and Chromatin. Mercury and silver in serum: analysed by sector field inductively coupled plasma–mass spectrometry. Statistical analyses: nonparametric tests were used. Mann–Whitney U-test was used for comparisons between the treatment group and the reference group. The Friedman test was used for comparisons of repeated measurements in the treatment group (baseline, and 3 and 12 months after removal of amalgam).
Bjorkman 2017, [Norway]; JAP ²⁹	Prospective longitudinal with pre-post and control	a) Health complaints - Questionnaire; SHC inventory; b) Personality variables - Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory-2 (MMPI-2), the PSY-5 scales; c) Global measure of life satisfaction - the Cantril Ladder Scale; Self-reported; Dentist examination d) trace elements – urine.	Mean change scores and 95% confidence interval; ANOVA for repeated measures; Greenhouse–Geisser correction was applied when the assumption of equal variances was violated. Standardised response means (SRM); Cochran's Q-test; correlational analyses.

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Sjursen 2011, [Norway]; JAP ³⁰	Prospective longitudinal with pre-post and control	Changes in local orofacial complaints and general health complaints from Questionnaire 1 (inclusion into study) to the 3-year follow-up in the treatment group and to Questionnaire 3 in the reference group. Before component: mercury concentration - blood/urine analysed by cold vapour atomic absorption spectrophotometry and mercury concentration in serum by sector field inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry. Patient health status: questionnaire - initial examination (1993–1999) then Questionnaire 1 (2000–2001). After treatment component: mercury concentration - blood/urine analysed. Patient subjective complaints: dental practitioner examination, enquiry with regards to side effects, post-operative dental pain and other complication. Reference group: questionnaires in 2004, 2007	Paired sample t-test; adjustments for age, gender, and complaint intensity reported in Questionnaire 1 were made by analysis of covariance.
Cabana-Munoz 2015, [Spain]; JAP ³¹	Cross-sectional with control	Hair samples were taken from all subjects and tested to determine heavy metal levels by inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICPMS). ICP-MS values for heavy metals were reported in µg/g of hair. These patients (women) had a medium/higher sociocultural status. SOD-1 activity was measured by the change in optical density at 560 nm for 2 min at 30/60 s intervals and normalised as Optical Density (D.O) by protein. Glutathione determination: Sodium phosphate (0.1 M) plus EDTA (5 mM) (pH 8.0) and H3PO4 (25%) were added to the samples. The plasma was centrifuged for 30 minutes at 13.000 r.p.m and supernatants were removed. Reduced glutathione levels were determined as follows: 200 µl of 40 mM N-ethylmaleimide and 100 µl of ortho-phthalaldehyde were added and fluorescence was measured at 350 m excitation and 420 nm emission, after 15 minutes of incubation at room temperature.	Mean and SD estimated for age and heavy metal levels in study group subjects' hair and in control subjects. Bonferroni and t Student test (2 tails) were applied to determine possible significant differences between women who had dental amalgam fillings vs controls. Nonparametric tests were applied when there was no homogeneity of variance (Mann Withney/Kruskal Wallis). Differences statistically significant when p<0.05 and highly significant when p<0.01.
Cabana-Munoz 2019, [Spain]; JAP ³²	Cross-sectional with control	Hair samples were collected close to the scalp. Heavy metals and/or oligoelements compared in hair samples from study groups by ICP-MS (Inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry). All expressed as µg/g of hair (Hg2+, Cu2+, Zn2+, Sn, Ti, Al, V, Ni, Cr, Co, Mo, Ba, Ca2+, Sr, Mn2+, Fe2+, I, Ge, P, S, Cd, Pb, Sb, As, Pt, Tl, Th, U). Thiobarbituric Acid Assay (TBARS): Malondialdehyde Levels (MDA) as an Index of Lipoperoxidation. TBA content quantified by interpolation within the standard curve and expressed as mg of MDA (MDA/mg protein); finally, all data were expressed as a percentage of the control group, which is 100%.	Means (SD) estimated for all evaluated parameters. Nonparametric Kruskal Wallis analysis performed for cases of non-homogeneity of variance if the Levene test was statistically significant (p < 0.05). The post hoc Mann Whitney or Dunn's analysis are nonparametric tests used for multiple comparisons among groups; the Dunn's task is applied for unequal sample size for comparisons between groups and controls subjects, respectively. The ANOVA identifies possible significant differences between groups in case of homogeneity of variance when the Levene test is not significant (p > 0.05). In this case, the post hoc Bonferroni test analysed multiple comparisons between groups. Differences were statistically significant if p < 0.05 and highly significant

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			when $p < 0.01$. Correlations between data evaluated by r Pearson or Spearman test.
Chen 2020, [Taiwan]; JAP ³³	Case control	Collected from the 2010 Longitudinal Health Insurance Database (LHID 2010). This study identified patients, from the LHID 2010, who had received amalgam fillings-related treatments according to procedure codes. Parkinson's Disease (PD) diagnoses defined according to ICD-9-CM code.	Confounding factors included in analysis: age, urbanisation level, Charlson Comorbidity Index (CCI), socioeconomic factors, sex. Continuous variables: student's t-test. Categorical variables: chi-square test with odds ratio (OR) for calculating between the control and case groups; and multiple logistic regression used in stratified analysis.
Chen 2021, [Taiwan]; JAP ³⁴	Case control	Identified patients from the 2010 Longitudinal Health Insurance Database (2010LHID). Disease diagnoses defined according to ICD-9-CM code. Individuals with AMF from LHID 2010 were validated by NHI treatment codes for health insurance reimbursement qualification.	Continuous variables: student's t-test. Categorical variables: chi-square test with odds ratio (OR) for calculating between the control and case groups; subgroup analysis: multiple logistic regression model. Adjustments were made for age, gender, income, region, and comorbidities.
Daniels 2007, [UK]; JAP ³⁵	Prospective cohort	Questionnaire to collect self-reported data of amalgam fillings and fish intake etc. Umbilical cord tissue taken at birth for Hg concentration. Gestational age and birthweight were ascertained from hospital records. ALSPAC adaptation of the MacArthur-Bates Communicative Development Inventory (MCDI) assessed the child's vocabulary comprehension and social communication at 15 months of age. The MCDI is a parent-completed assessment of the child's language development and general development.	Birth outcomes were adjusted for the child's sex, birth order and maternal age, fish consumption, prenatal smoking, prenatal alcohol use and level of educational achievement according to the English system. The analysis of birthweight was also adjusted for gestational age. The association between dental care and language development was further adjusted for the child's age at testing, breastfeeding, weekly fish consumption at age 12 months, and the quality of the parent and home environment, represented by a self-completion adaptation by ALSPAC of the Home Observation for Measurement of the Environment (HOME) score (continuous).
Dermata 2018, [Greece]; JAP ³⁶	RCT	Clinical assessment of restorations at baseline and semi-annually. Radiographic assessment: annually. All restorations assessed by 4 paediatric dentists and instructors in Paediatric Dentistry Clinic (not involved in restoration placement) using modified USPHS criteria covering: presence of restoration; marginal integrity; proximal contacts; anatomical form (including occlusal wear); gingival health; and presence of secondary caries. Any restoration graded as C was considered unacceptable and had to be replaced.	Descriptive statistics calculated as frequencies for all United States Public Health Service (USPHS) criteria. Crude differences between USPHS criteria assessment of two groups initially checked with Fisher exact tests, then differences in performance for each USPHS criterion separately and as overall all-cause failure (failure of minimum one USPHS criterion) assessed with generalised linear regression modelling for binary family (bivariable analyses for each outcome were fitted, considering clustering of multiple restorations within a patient with standard errors, while reporting RR and corresponding 95% CI). Potentially confounding effects from: patient gender, age, tooth type, and jaw controlled for by calculating adjusted RRs from multivariable models, following pre-defined protocol. Each confounder inserted in separate bivariable model/outcome. Confounders with $P < 0.2$ in this model included in multivariable model with randomised material. All

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			analyses in Stata per protocol with two-sided $P \leq 0.05$. No ancillary analyses was planned or performed.
Duame, 2021, [Germany]; JAP ³⁷	Cross-sectional with control group	Dental materials documented and association of oral lichen planus (OLP) with metal/amalgam followed the Thornhill criteria: Type 1 - no association; Type II - weak association; Type III - strong association; Type IV - very strong association.	Logistic regression: analyse the interaction between “presentation form” with “gender”, “reticular lichen”, and the presence of “gold” and “composite” restorations. Significance= $p=0.05$.
Eyson 2010, [UK]; JAP ³⁸	Retrospective record review	Skin patch testing: (European Standard and Dental Material series (Trolab Biodiagnostics Ltd: Hermal Patch Test Allergens)) if any oral lichenoid reactions/sore mouth reported at consultation. Patches placed on patient's back and result read after 48 hours by clinician. Blood and urine mercury measured.	Venous blood and urine samples analysed using Varian SpectrAA 20 (Varian Ltd, Oxford UK). Analyses performed by cold vapour atomic absorption (AA) spectrometry with deuterium arc background correction. T-tests and ANOVA compared mean differences Hg levels in blood/urine among groups (gender, age groups, presenting complaints, and medical conditions). For number of amalgams between groups: Chi-square test. For complaints and medical conditions significant in t-tests, ANOVA or Chi-square testing for trend, multiple logistic regressions further analysed to compute age and gender adjusted OR for Hg levels in blood or urine, or number of amalgams.
Forkel 2024, [Germany, Switzerland and Austria]; JAP ³⁹	Retrospective record review	Patients' histories, clinical data and patch test results recorded in local databases at participating centres, transferred to Information Network of Departments of Dermatology (IVDK) central office University Medical Centre of Göttingen, Germany. Patch test reactions: day 3 or 4 considered for analysis. Patch test exposure time: 24 hours (23.6%) and 48 hours (76.4%) patients. Finn Chambers (8 mm inner diameter) on Scanpor (SmartPractice Europe, Greven, Germany) used in 95.1% patch tests.	Data analysis stratified for final diagnoses. Percentages of proportions of items from the patients' histories or reaction frequencies in disjunct groups of patients were presented together with exact 95% Cis.
Frisk 2007, [Sweden]; JAP ⁴⁰	Controlled before and after	Collection for Clinical Chemistry Parameters: No food intake allowed after 10pm before sampling. Sampling took place between 8:00 and 10:00am, 2 samples of venous blood drawn using stainless steel needles and 2 different tubes: a 7-ml Vacutainer® tube with EDTA for whole blood sampling (first tube) and 7-ml Vacutainer® tube with gel and coagulation activator for serum sampling both from Becton Dickinson AB, Stockholm, Sweden. Blood sampling performed before and at least one year after dental amalgam removal and other metal alloys supported by antioxidant therapy.	Mann–Whitney's U test used to test differences between patients and controls in each clinical chemistry variable. Wilcoxon's sign-rank test used to test the difference between before and after treatment in each patient. Multivariate method discriminant function analysis used to investigate if the three groups could be separated when using all clinical data simultaneously.
Franzblau 2012, [USA]; JAP ⁴¹	Longitudinal with cross-sectional element	Nerve conduction. Electrodiagnostic studies of the median and ulnar sensory nerves were conducted in the dominant hand using established techniques. Tests were performed using antidromic, supramaximal stimulation, a stimulation-to-recording distance of 14 cm, and ring-recording electrodes placed around digits two and five. Hand temperature was recorded and hand was warmed if the mid-palmar temperature was	Descriptive statistics included means, SD, proportions, medians and ranges. Histograms were used to illustrate distributional forms. Covariates used in regression analyses were collected in the same year in which the urine mercury and nerve conduction data were collected. Linear regression was performed to analyse the earliest year of data for each individual, and repeated measures models (using the SAS Mixed

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		<p>below 32 8C. Only peak latencies were considered. Nerves that had an absent response during nerve conduction testing were assigned a value for latency equal to 3 standard deviations (SD) above the study sample mean and a value for the amplitude equal to the lowest recorded amplitude in the study sample (n = 12; 0.3%) Mercury exposure. Mercury assayed in spot urine samples based on a single void. All samples held at 48 C until analysis, which was conducted at the ADA laboratory in Chicago, using a cold vapor atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The limit of detection (LOD) for urinary mercury analyses was 0.2 mg/L. Urine mercury concentration levels below the LOD were assigned a value of (LOD)/(square root of 2) (n = 22, 0.5%). Urine mercury levels in general population obtained from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) 1999–2000 survey. Health Questionnaire. Subjects reported age (at the time of examination), sex, height and weight, dental specialty, number of years in practice, medical history (including history of diabetes mellitus (DM), carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS), or rheumatoid arthritis (RA)), number of amalgams placed and removed by the subject on a weekly basis, as well as the frequency of hand, wrist, and finger pain occurrence. Self-reported height and weight were used to compute the body mass index (BMI) as (weight in kilograms)/(height in meters)² (kg/m²).</p>	<p>procedure) were used to analyse all observations from each subject over time. Both urine mercury concentrations and nerve conduction measures were incorporated in regression models as continuous variables. Additionally, models of nerve conduction parameters were assessed with urine mercury categorised into quartiles. All models included covariates that may have confounded the relationship between urine mercury concentrations and nerve function, including BMI, age, gender, and hand temperature, and also ‘dummy’ variables for each of the years the data were collected. Sensitivity analysis: Some subjects within the sample had urine mercury concentrations considerably higher than the background mercury exposure in the general population; to assess whether urine mercury in the range that was relevant to the general population had an impact on measured nerve function, all models with and without these ‘high’ observations were performed. Observations with urine mercury concentrations at or above 10.4 mg/L (n = 156) were excluded. Average past exposures of dental professionals to mercury vapour were likely higher than recent exposures, particularly among older dentists so the models were repeated after excluding subjects age 55 or older at the time of testing.</p>
Gavic 2019, [Croatia]; JAP ⁴²	RCT	<p>Personal characteristics (health status, use of medication, X-ray exposure), and dietary aspects collected through questionnaire. Sample collection: samples of epithelial cells collected using the swab technique; immediately before (control), and 7, 30 and 90 days following the restoration of the tooth by gently brushing the gingival area along the glass-ionomer or compomer restoration with an interdental brush and applied to encoded microscopic slides pre-warmed at 37°C. Micronucleus Assay in Buccal Epithelial Cells: cells were allowed to air-dry and then fixed in methanol (80% v/v) at 4 °C for 20 minutes. Staining was carried out and after slides were rinsed with distilled water and airdried. Analysis done under a light microscope with 400× magnification and each micronucleus and other nuclear anomalies additionally verified under 1,000× magnification. Two replicate slides were prepared for each subject, and 1,000 epithelium cells per preparation were scored for each sampling time. Frequencies of nuclear abnormalities also evaluated and classified. Cells with two nuclei were considered binucleate. Nuclear anomalies recorded separately.</p>	<p>Descriptive statistical analysis to determine the basic statistical parameters (mean, standard error, standard deviation, and relative standard deviation, median and minimum and maximum values). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) using a general linear model procedure. Difference among the tested groups assessed by analysis of variance and Tukey HSD post hoc test. Multiple regression analysis, General Regression Model (GRM) from linear/nonlinear modelling method and canonical correlation analysis for assessment of the predictor variables influence (age, gender, state of health and use of medication, X-ray exposure, and dietary habits) on dependent variables (number of micronucleated and binucleated cells, cells with nucleoplasmic bridges, nuclear buds, pyknosis, condensed chromatin and karyorrhexis). The results of GRM were expressed in the form of Pareto charts of t values. Statistical significance was set at p<0.05.</p>

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De Rouen 2006, [Portugal]; JAP ⁴³ (De Rouen, 2002)	RCT	All primary outcomes assessed annually. Neurobehavioural tests: administered by 3 psychometrists. Memory - Rey Auditory Verbal Learning and Visual learning tests. Attention/concentration: Coding, Symbol Search, Digit span, Finger Windows, Stroop, and Trails A and B. Motor/visuomotor: Finger Tapping, Drawing (through follow up year 3), Matching, Pegboard, and Standard Reaction Time. From fourth follow up years: adult versions substituted for child equivalents: Wechsler Memory Scale-R Visual Reproductions; Spatial Span from the Wechsler Memory Scale-III, Matrix Reasoning from the Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence (WASI), and Symbol Search, Coding, and Digit Span subtests from the Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale III (WAIS). Nerve conduction velocity tests: performed by 1 technician, with trained substitutes if needed. Secondary outcomes: CTONI at baseline and year 7 and WASI. US norms used. Single -void urine samples: baseline and annual visits. Renal response: Urinary glutathione transferases (GST- and GST-) and porphyrins. Renal glomerular function monitored using creatinine-adjusted urinary albumin concentrations. Hg Exposure: continuous cold-flow, cold-vapor atomic spectrofluorometry, using a PSA Merlin Mercury Analysis. Urinary creatinine: colorimetric determination assay kit. Cumulative amalgam: units of surface-years, was obtained from the number of amalgam restoration surfaces placed, weighted by time each restoration in place. Sentinal Adverse Health Events: Responses of parents or guardians to annual health history questionnaires, and teacher reports.	Multivariate statistical analysis: 1) O'Brien test, 2) Hotelling T2 test (2-tailed approach). Significance level of .05 divided between both tests. Univariate methods: mean z scores for treatment groups for each primary outcome annually (95% confidence intervals). Wilcoxon rank sum test: annual comparisons between creatinine adjusted albumin levels. Z-test: compare treatment groups on follow-up creatinine-adjusted urinary mercury. Intention-to-treat used for all analyses, all data available on all randomised patients included. Those who did not complete 7 years of follow-up: censored at last available follow-up. Missing data: impact assessed at study completion.
Geier 2011, [USA]; JAP ⁴⁴	RCT (secondary analysis)	Urine sample (*50 ml) was collected from each child at baseline and at each subsequently scheduled annual visit to the University of Lisbon School of Dental Medicine for dental, neurological, and neurobehavioral evaluations. Porphyrins were quantitated in the remaining unacidified portion of the urine sample by high-performance liquid chromatography. Measurements of urinary porphyrin concentrations (lg/L) were analysed: uroporphyrin (uP), heptacarboxyporphyrin (7cxP), hexacarboxyporphyrin (6cxP), 5cxP, PrcP, and cP.	Two-tailed P-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. An individual's exposure was measured by counting the number of amalgam restorations of the buccal, distal, lingual, and occlusal surfaces. An exposure score for each individual was computed by applying scores of 1.0, 2.0, or 3.0 for small, medium, or large restorations, respectively, then adding these scores for each restoration of each tooth for each year. A weighting scheme was used to create the yearly exposure scores for subsequent analyses. Repeated measures were collected for each subject, a mixed-effects repeated-measures model was used to estimate the relationship between exposure and outcome. Each model included terms for subject age as the repeated measurement factor, exposure, and the following covariates: gender, race, baseline level (i.e. study year 1) of urinary Hg, baseline measurements of each urinary porphyrin measures, and the baseline level of lead (Pb) in each subject's blood.

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Geier 2013, [USA]; JAP ⁴⁵	RCT (Prospective cohort)	Neurobehavioral, neurological, renal function, urinary Hg, and urinary porphyrin assessments. Information regarding composition, number, size, and positioning of dental fillings. Urine sample (*50 ml) collected at baseline and each annual visit for dental, neurological, and neurobehavioral evaluations. Concentrations of GSTS-a and -p in urine samples measured by enzyme immunoassay employing kits (Biotrin USA (Cedarknolls, New Jersey, USA).	Original dataset from parent study was not modified. Mixed-effects repeated-measures model used to estimate relationship between exposure and outcome. Each model included terms for subject, including the repeated measurement factor, exposure, and the following covariates: gender, race, baseline level (i.e. study year 1) of urinary Hg, baseline measurements of each urinary porphyrin measures (uroporphyrin, heptacarboxyporphyrin, hexacarboxyporphyrin, pentacarboxyporphyrin, precopropophyrin, and coproporphyrin), and the baseline level of lead in each subject's blood. Interaction terms were added if they contributed.
Lauterbach 2008, [Portugal]; JAP ⁴⁶	RCT	Neurological examinations by 1 of 2 neurologists obtained before beginning dental treatment at baseline and at yearly follow-up examinations for seven subsequent years. included brief evaluation mental status (consciousness; language; and orientation to person, time and place), observation of cranial nerve function, gross motor function (muscle strength and tone and deep tendon reflexes), plantar responses, cerebellar functions (including limb and gait coordination), touch, joint position and vibration senses and recording of involuntary movements (such as athetosis or chorea). Adventitious movements (including tremor) added during year1 follow-up. Introduced neurological soft signs (NSS) screening second year follow up. NSS severity scores added follow-up year 3.	Proportion patients each treatment group exhibiting NSSs, tremor, NSSs/year recorded. Means/SD of NSS severity scores within treatment groups for follow-up years 3-7. Compared treatment groups: Fisher exact test for proportions and two-sample Student t test for mean severity scores.
Martin 2008, [Portugal & USA]; JAP ⁴⁷	RCT	507 children (8-12 years at baseline) participated in the RCT to examine the potential health effects of exposure to dental materials, followed for 7 years with an extensive battery of neurobehavioral, renal, and neurological evaluations. Two treatment groups: (i) dental composites only; (ii) mercury/silver dental amalgam where appropriate (primarily in posterior teeth such as molars and premolars). Children followed for 7 years from study enrolment date. Annual examination: a spot urine sample was taken for measurement of creatinine as well as other target chemicals. Urine sample collected in a sterile, capped 100-mL urine collection cup. A sample was provided of at least one third (volume) of the cup and frozen until analysis. Urinary creatinine concentrations were measured using a standard colorimetric procedure.	Urinary creatinine means, confidence intervals, and 10th, 50th, and 90th percentiles calculated by year of age for entire group, by sex, and by race (whites, blacks). Race, sex, and age effects on average creatinine assessed using multivariate linear regression. Generalised estimating equations: potential correlation between measurements at different times on same study participant. Wald tests: overall sexual effect, overall differences between blacks and whites and for trend.
Roberts 2008, [Portugal]; JAP ⁴⁸	RCT (amalgam arm only - prospective cohort)	Baseline samples collected after dental treatment (3-6mnth), and 7 annual follow-up visits. Oral samples collected by dental hygienist: BBL™ CultureSwab™ Transport System (Becton Dickinson, Sparks, MD, USA) from buccal mucosa (lower right quadrant) and right buccal gingival. Swabs	Logistic regression: compared proportion of children with antibiotic-resistance or Hgr bacteria at post-baseline visits in each treatment group. Covariates: race, gender, study year, indicator of antibiotic-specific baseline growth in child. Used GEE and exchangeable working

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		<p>placed 1 mL PRAS buffer (0.038 M NaCl, 1.073 mM KCl, 2.05 mM sodium thiosulfate, 1 mM resazurin, and 23 mM L-cystein), vortexed 1 min, serially diluted 10-fold in PRAS buffer, plated onto Blood Agar plates and 5% sheep's blood, 5g/mL hemin, and 0.05 g/mL vitamin K]. Some plates supplemented with ampicillin (Ap), erythromycin (Em), or tetracycline (Tc) at 10g/mL, 5g/mL, or 4g/mL. Brain Heart Infusion Agar (BHI) (Difco) and BHI supplemented with 200 M HgCl₂, made weekly, used starting with 1 year follow-up. Plates incubated at 36.5°C under 5% CO₂ for 4-72 hours before colonies counted. Midstream urine collected, 10-mL quantity transferred to sterile conical tube, centrifuged at 3000rpm for 15min and decanted. Samples serially diluted (1:10) in PRAS buffer, and a 100-μL quantity from each dilution was plated onto MacConkey media (MAC) without crystal violet (Difco Lab.) and MAC supplemented with 25g/mL ampicillin, chloramphenicol, or tetracycline. At 1 year follow-up, samples plated on MAC supplemented with 200 M HgCl₂. Plates incubated 37°C aerobically for 24-48 hours and counted to give numbers of bacteria/mL of urine. Percentage of children with Hgr bacteria determined with number of positive samples for growth on unsupplemented MAC as denominator. Urinary mercury concentrations previously determined.</p>	<p>correlation matrix, to account for correlations between multiple outcome measurements on same child. Compared numbers antibiotic-resistant or Hgr bacteria in each group using linear regression models applied to log₁₀-transformed bacteria counts (same covariates as above and log-count for unsupplemented plate as additional covariate). Log-transformed counts used to stabilise variance and provide approximate normally distributed dependent variables. GEE method to account for correlations described above. For oral samples: average bacteria counts for gingival and buccal mucosal samples used. Intention-to-treat analysis used. Additional analyses: generalized estimating equations (GEE) and logistic regression: associations between antibiotic and Hg resistance (controlled study year, gender, race) and tested associations between Hgr or Apr bacteria in urine and presence of Hgr or Apr bacteria in oral samples.</p>
Woods 2008, [Portugal]; JAP ⁴⁹	RCT	<p>Concentrations of GSTs-a and -p in urine samples were measured by enzyme immunoassay employing kits purchased from Biotrin USA (Cedarknolls, NJ, USA). Assay procedure was based on the sequential addition of sample, enzyme-conjugate and substrate to microtiter wells coated with anti-a or anti-p GST IgG. A Molecular Devices UV-Max microplate reader capable of 96 simultaneous UV absorbance determinations was employed for GST quantitation. Urinary albumin was quantitated using a radial immunodiffusion assay (The Binding Site, San Diego, CA, USA). Creatinine concentrations were measured using a standard colorimetric procedure (Sigma no. 555-A; Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA).</p>	<p>Analyses on log-transformed concentrations. Descriptive statistics for creatinine-adjusted values of GST-a, GST-p, and albumin on the natural logarithm scale by treatment group and year of age. Treatment groups compared across years of age by fitting linear regression models using generalised estimating equations. Separate regression models run for each of three log transformed concentrations (GST-a, GST-p, and albumin) as outcome variables. Main predictor variable=treatment group. Covariates: log-transformed creatinine concentration, year of age (9–18), baseline age at baseline, gender, race. Separate analyses conducted with baseline values of outcome variable and log-transformed creatinine as additional covariates. Urinary mercury not included as predictor variable.</p>
Woods 2009, [Portugal]; JAP ⁵⁰	RCT	<p>Urine sample collected at baseline and each annual follow-ups. 10-ml aliquot removed and acidified with 1 N HCl for use in Hg analysis by continuous flow, cold-vapor spectrofluorometry. Porphyrins quantitated in unacidified portion of urine sample by high-performance liquid chromatography. Urinary creatinine concentrations measured in unacidified urine using colorimetric procedure (Sigma number 555-A).</p>	<p>Urine samples with uro/coproporphyrin concentrations <2 μg/L were excluded. Concentrations of other porphyrins below detection limit in samples with acceptable uro- and coproporphyrin values set at 0.05 μg/L so positive value for these porphyrins included in the log transformations for computation of geometric means. Analyses performed on log-transformed porphyrin concentrations. Mixed</p>

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Methods	Analysis
			models: adjust log-transformed porphyrin/creatinine ratios for baseline log-transformed porphyrin/creatinine ratio and account for inter-individual variation in porphyrins. Separate linear regression model for each porphyrin. Each regression model adjusted for age, gender, race, follow up year, log-transformed urinary creatinine (g/L), and baseline log-transformed porphyrin/creatinine ratio ($\mu\text{g/g}$).
Halperin-Sternfeld 2016, [Israel]; JAP ⁵¹	Retrospective cohort (records review)	Peridontal charts at T0 (baseline), T1 (following cause-related therapy), and T2 (≥ 10 years after T0). Data on general health parameters, medications, smoking status were collected. Data on restorations on interproximal sites were collected from patients' radiographs. The type of the restoration (amalgam/composite/FPDs), its contour (under/over contour), the presence of overhang or open margins, and the presence of secondary caries were recorded. Teeth were recorded as having a new restoration if the change could be visible on later radiographs. Extractions were recorded and classified to those extracted due to periodontal causes and those extracted due to non-periodontal causes. Radiographic analysis, including classification of restorations - performed by two graduate students in periodontology (MHS and MS) in a joint session until reaching agreement. Data were collected on general health parameters, medications and smoking status.	Association between periodontal disease incidence and progression was assessed in relation to teeth restorative status, initial probing pocket depths (PPD), smoking habits, and frequency of supportive periodontal therapy (SPT). Two levels for the units of statistical analysis: (i) surface and (ii) tooth levels. (i) Deepest PPD measurement in each proximal surface (mesiobuccal or mesiolingual/-palatal and distobuccal or distolingual/-palatal in the mesial and distal surfaces, respectively) was used. BOP was recorded as positive if found in at least one of the two sites in each proximal surface. Mean PPD at T0, T1, and T2 were calculated and compared between unrestored and restored surfaces using Mann-Whitney U test, and between unrestored surfaces, surfaces exhibiting adequate restorations, and surfaces exhibiting inadequate restorations, using analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Bonferroni correction. (ii) Tooth levels teeth were categorised as either exhibiting PPD < 5 mm or PPD ≥ 5 mm, according to their deepest initial PPD value in one of the four interproximal sites examined (mesiobuccal, mesiolingual/-palatal, distobuccal, and distolingual/-palatal). BOP was recorded as positive if found in at least one of the four sites examined in each tooth. Association between PPD progression and restorative status was examined using chi-square analysis: teeth were categorised as either exhibiting PPD < 5 mm or PPD ≥ 5 mm according to their initial deepest PPD value. Analyses were performed for all teeth, for unrestored and restored teeth, and for teeth exhibiting adequate and inadequate restorations. Changes in PPD were evaluated during cause-related therapy (between T0 and T1) and during maintenance (between T1 and T2). Numbers and percentages of teeth that received new restorations and teeth extracted were calculated. Changes in PPD, extraction rates, and the percentages of teeth that received new restorations were evaluated in relation to smoking status, initial PPD, and frequency of SPT. PPD progression was calculated as changes in the

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Methods	Analysis
			distributions of teeth exhibiting PPD < 5 mm and PPD ≥ 5 mm, between T0 and T1 and between T1 and T2. PPD progression was compared between the various subgroups. The level of statistical significance was set at 5%.
Hsu 2016, [Taiwan]; JAP ⁵²	Retrospective cohort – nested case control	Data collected from National Health Insurance Research Database (NHIRD) patient registry. Amalgam filling status determined by code record of amalgam filling (89001C–89003C and 89101C–89103C). Patient demographic characteristics included encrypted identification numbers, sex, dates of birth and death, and diagnostic data and procedures. Diagnostic data included the dates of dental procedures and the International Classification of Diseases, Ninth Revision, Clinical Modification (ICD-9-CM). For the non-amalgam filling cohort, a 1:1 paired matching was used for each amalgam filling, patient by sex, age, and index date. Parkinson’s Disease (PD)-related comorbidities recorded if diagnosed twice or more and Charlson-Deyo Comorbidity Index (CCI) calculated for each participant. Cohorts were followed from the index date until the PD diagnosis, death, or the end of the year 2008, whichever came first.	Demographic characteristics and baseline comorbidities were compared between the amalgam and non-amalgam filling cohorts. McNemar’s tests for categorical variables and paired samples t-test for continuous variables were used. The incidence rate (per 1000 person-years) calculated by dividing the number of events of current PD by the person-years observed for each patient. The Kaplan-Meier method was used to assess the survival probability in PD between the amalgam and non-amalgam filling cohorts and log-rank test used to compare differences. Univariate and multivariable models were then used to calculate the hazard ratios (HRs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) with the Cox proportional-hazards regression models. Multivariable models were adjusted for age; comorbidities of diabetes, hypertension and hyperlipidaemia; and moderate CCI. Statistical significance: p-value <0.05.
Hu 2021, [Taiwan]; JAP ⁵³	Cross-sectional with control	Data from the Longitudinal Health Insurance Database (LHID) 2010 database. The LHID 2010 collected registration information and dental and medical data. The codes 89,004, 89,005, 89,008, 89,009, 89,010, 89,012,89,104, 89,105, 89,108, 89,109, 89,110, and 89,112 for operative dentistry (OD) treatment indicate composite resin restoration. Patients were followed from the first date for composite resin restoration until 5 years after the date OD treatment was received. The diagnosis of ADHD was according to ICD-9 codes 314.00, 314.01, and 314.9. Only two or more repeated diagnoses of ADHD in one year during 2005–2013 were considered to ensure accurate diagnostic criteria. The date on which each patient was first diagnosed with ADHD was defined as the index date.	Statistical analyses of demographic characteristics and socioeconomic status of study subjects were performed using Student’s t-test for continuous variables and the chi-squared test for categorical variables. Conditional logistic regression was used to estimate crude and adjusted odds ratios (ORs) with a 95% confidence interval (CI) for the case group compared with the control group. In multivariate analysis, adjustments were made for age and sex. Psychiatric comorbidities including autism, mental retardation, and developmental delay were assessed as the confounding factors in this study.
Lartitegui-Sebastian 2012, [Spain], JAP ⁵⁴	Prospective Clinical Observational Study with a Pre-post design	Lichenoid lesions of the oral mucosa: identified and qualified according to previously established criteria. Specific protocol designed to analyse location, physical appearance, symmetry and bilateral character of the lesions and their topographic relationship with silver amalgam restorations. Restorations: number, location, condition and colour of the surface (smooth/rough, silver/blackish) assessed. Patch tests: performed on all patients with lichenoid lesions. Allergen battery was designed specifically in relation to the amalgam.	A statistic descriptive and comparative analysis was performed.

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Methods	Analysis
Leybovich 2014, [USA]; JAP ⁵⁵	RCT (1-arm relevant)	Dental parameters recorded baseline and 3 months post-operation by clinician: gingival index (GI), plaque index (PI), probing depths (PD), percentage bleeding on probing (BOP), gingival recession (GR) on labial/buccal surface, clinical attachment levels (CAL) and keratinized gingiva (KG). Self-report: dentinal hypersensitivity (DH).	All data analysed using Wilcoxon signed rank test with statistical significance at $p \leq .05$.
Lin 2017, [Taiwan]; JAP ⁵⁶	Retrospective cohort	Taiwan National Health Insurance Program: records of the Longitudinal Health Insurance Database 2005 (LHID2005), which includes registration data and dental and medical claims filed between 2001 and 2011 of 1,000,000 beneficiaries randomly sampled from all national health insurance beneficiaries in 2005.	Comparisons between exposed and nonexposed groups in ADHD incidence and demographic and clinical characteristics: paired Student's t tests and McNemar's tests. Log-rank test and univariate and multivariate Cox proportional hazards models used to estimate effect of amalgam restorations on risk of ADHD during study period. Confounding factors (i.e. age, sex, number of tooth restorations, fluoride varnish application, medical institution, urbanisation level and systemic diseases) adjusted in Cox regression analyses. Subgroup analyses performed according to age, sex and number of amalgam restorations. Significance $P < 0.05$ (two-tailed).
Louopou 2020, [Canada]; JAP ⁵⁷	Prospective cohort	Mercury concentration - maternal blood; blood pressure; diagnostic criteria for gestational hypertension (GH) based on Society of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists of Canada guidelines; Dental amalgam – Patient questionnaire; clinical data throughout pregnancy abstracted from medical charts.	Potential covariates: maternal age at delivery (years), parity, ethnicity (Caucasian, non-Caucasian), body mass index (BMI) before pregnancy, weight gain during pregnancy, education, household income, maternal smoking, fish consumption, coffee intake, multiple child pregnancy, women with autoimmune disease. Descriptive statistics for maternal characteristics. Comparisons for continuous variables: Student's T-test or univariate ANOVA, Mann-Whitney or Kruskal-Wallis tests and for categorical variables using chi-square tests. Medians (interquartile range (IQR)) and geometric means (GM) Hg concentration determined according to dental amalgam status and compared using Mann-Whitney or Kruskal-Wallis. Spearman correlation to test correlations between blood Hg, dental amalgam status and fish consumption. Logistic regression: explore association between dental amalgam status and GH. Presence of dental amalgams assessed according to number (categorized as 0, 1–4 and ≥ 5) and time reported. Analysed impact of replacements. Crude and adjusted ORs and 95% CI estimated using logistic regression. Adjustment made for covariates selected either a priori or empirically. Examined other covariates separately for potential confounding bias using change-in-estimate method. Those that changed ORs of association between dental amalgam status and GH by $\pm 10\%$ considered confounder and included in multivariable model. Missing data ignored. Each data point statistically analysed according to

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Methods	Analysis
			trimester reported. Sensitivity analyses conducted: (1) including covariates missing data in the model, and (2) excluding participants who reported data at first trimester but missing data at third trimester. Linear generalised estimating equations (GEE): explore relationship between dental amalgam status and systolic or diastolic blood pressure (SBP or DBP). Models incorporated first-order autoregressive correlation pattern for the repeated events. This model considered automatically the value of first trimester when missing in the third trimester and vice versa. (p) < 0.05 indicated statistical significance.
Lygre 2013, [Norway]; JAP ⁵⁸	Controlled before and after	Questionnaire 1 (207/358): education, recent dental treatment, current health complaints (including orofacial). Mercury concentration: blood/urine analysed by cold vapour atomic absorption spectrophotometry and mercury concentration in serum by sector field inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry. Data collected from 20 participants: medical examination, dental examination, blood/urine samples, questionnaire 2 - intensity of health complaints. Questionnaire 3 - completed 3 years after amalgam filling removal, intensity of orofacial and general health complaints. External reference group questionnaire: (441/800) intensities of the participants' health complaints.	Paired sample t-test: differences in symptom scores before and 3 years after amalgam replacement. Mann-Whitney U-test and independent-sample t-test: differences between groups. Spearman's correlation: to examine correlations between variables. Effect size for differences between symptoms at pretreatment/3 year follow-up: SRM. Values of ‡0.20, ‡0.50 and ‡ 0.80: represent small, moderate and large responsiveness, respectively. p-value equal to or less than 0.05 - statistically significant.
Lygre 2016, [Norway]; JAP ⁵⁹	Prospective cohort	Two questionnaires: weeks 17 and 30 of pregnancy. Demographic and health information and prenatal amalgam exposure from dental treatment/number of teeth amalgam fillings. Self-report total number of teeth and total number of teeth with amalgam fillings. Linked to data from Medical Birth Registry of Norway (MBRN): gender, malformations, stillbirth, birthweight, and preterm delivery.	Correlation between number of teeth with amalgam fillings and birthweight: Pearson correlation coefficient. OR (95% CI) for early preterm delivery (<32 weeks), late preterm (33–36 weeks), low birthweight (<2500 g) for all births and for births at 37–42 weeks, stillbirth, and malformations by level amalgam exposure: Logistic regression. Confounders adjusted for mother's age, maternal education, smoking during pregnancy, alcohol consumption during pregnancy, parity, and BMI before pregnancy. Pregnancies with missing information included in analyses as separate category within relevant variable. Statistical significance: P-values: < 0.05.
Lygre 2018, [Norway]; JAP ⁶⁰	Prospective cohort	Questionnaires: Week 17 (Q1) and 30 (Q3) pregnancy and child 3 (Q6) and 5 (Q7) years. Q3: Self-reported information regarding prenatal exposure dental amalgam and amalgam exposure during pregnancy. Removal amalgam fillings. Q6/Q7: ADHD symptoms, using items from Child Behaviour Checklist (CBCL) and symptom list for ADHD from DSM-IV-TR at Q6 and items from Conners' Parent Rating Scale (CPRS) and ADHD index at Q7	Only singleton births/pregnancies with valid data on weight and height included in analyses. Genders analysed separately and together. ADHD symptom scores summarised separately for children when three/ five years. A sum score of ADHD symptoms above 90th percentile=high level of symptoms. Logistic regression analyses, odds ratios with 95% confidence intervals calculated: having sum scores at 90th percentile or higher by level of amalgam exposure (both as a continuous variable and categorised as 0, 1–4, 5–8 and ≥9 teeth with amalgam fillings; 0

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Methods	Analysis
			amalgam fillings used as reference). OR with 95% confidence intervals calculated for having sum scores at 90 th percentile or above by new amalgam fillings placed/amalgam fillings removed. Effects adjusted for: mother's age, maternal education, smoking during pregnancy, alcohol consumption during pregnancy, parity, and BMI before pregnancy. Pregnancies with missing information for maternal education, smoking habits and alcohol consumption during pregnancy included in analyses as a separate category. P-values < 0.05 statistically significant.
Lynch 2015, [Ireland]; JAP ⁶¹	Retrospective cohort with before and after component	Patient medical histories were reviewed. IQ Ultra Chambers applied to patients' backs and removed after 48 hours. Patients tested to British Society of Cutaneous Allergy standard series (n=30), dental screening and amalgam series (n=31) and dental methacrylate series (n=1). Patch test results read by 1 of 2 consultant dermatologists on days 2 and 4, and in many patients, readings taken on day 7. Macular reactions graded as T, papular reactions graded as +, and papulovesicular reactions graded as ++ in accordance with the International Contact Dermatitis Research Group criteria. Medical records reviewed after patch testing to assess clinical progress. Photographic records were taken.	Descriptive statistics (%) of number and type of positive and negative reactions to mercury and patterns of OLL. N (%) resolution of symptoms following amalgam removal per allergy group reported.
Ma 2021, [Taiwan]; JAP ⁶²	Retrospective observational: nested case control	Reimbursement data (1997- 2013) from Longitudinal Health Insurance Database 2000 (LHID 2000). Sociodemographic information: outpatient, inpatient, emergency care medical records and surgical and prescription history. Presence of disease: International Classification of Diseases, Ninth Revision, Clinical Modification (ICD-9-CM) diagnostic coding system. Peer-reviewed system confirmed diagnosis, all insurance claims monitored by medical reimbursement specialists. Propensity score matching to minimise effect of confounding factors. Oral lichen planus (OLP) diagnosis made by oral medicine or oral pathology specialists following modified WHO criteria (Final diagnosis fulfilled both clinical and histopathologic criteria.) Exposed materials: amalgam and composite resins for restorative procedures. Times of dental restorations calculated to estimate material exposure.	Covariates and confounding factors: Age, sex, potential confounding factors including socioeconomic status, comorbidities, and medical history involving frequency of outpatient visits, length of hospitalisation, and frequency of dental visits within 5 years prior to index date included and matched to select the non-OLP controls. Exposure to dental restorations and other dental treatments including root canal therapy and tooth extraction, considered to estimate effect of other treatment procedures on odds of OLP, and eliminate the interference of these conditions on outcome. Statistical analysis: Categorical variables including numbers and percentages delineated and analysed using chi-squared or Fisher exact test. Conditional logistic regression to estimate ORs and 95% CIs for case and control groups. Multivariate analysis: covariates associated with OLP adjusted. Inverse propensity score weighting used, standardised difference value derived to evaluate difference between case and control group. Values of standardised difference larger than 0.2 in the effect size analysis considered significant. p value < 0.05 statistically significant.
Marell 2014, [Sweden]; JAP ⁶³	Retrospective cohort with	Baseline and follow-up examination: clinical examination of patients and oral mucosa, types of dental restorations, intra-oral colour pictures, patch	Chi-square tests: differences between lichenoid contact reactions (LCR) and oral lichen planus groups regarding regression OLL; differences

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Methods	Analysis
	before and after component	test for hypersensitivity reactions to substances in dental materials. Replacement of dental restorations: no replacement, partial replacement (minimum removal of 1 but not all, of restorations in suspected material adjacent to lichenoid lesion) or total replacement (replacement of all suspected dental restorations, irrespective of whether in close contact with lesions or remote). Dental treatment from ordinary dentists. Baseline and follow-up questionnaires: dental and medical history, occupational history, use of drugs. All patients screened for psychological parameters: Symptom Checklist (SCL-90) and Global Severity Index (GSI). General stress the past year: General Perceived Stress Questionnaire (PSQ).	regarding regression of lesions between LCR patients with no, partial or total exchange of suspected materials; differences regarding regression of lesions after exchange of dental materials compared LCR patients with positive and negative patch test reactions. ANOVA: differences between two groups and reference group regarding psychological parameters GSI and PSQ. Significance $p=0.05$.
German Amalgam Trial			
Melchart 2008, [Germany]; JAP ⁶⁴	RCT	Baseline: toxicological, psychiatric, and dental screenings. Concomitant treatment, compliance with medication regimen in removal-plus group and participation in health promotion sessions in no-removal group, and occurrence of serious adverse events documented by physician each visit. Total and inorganic mercury levels: determined in plasma and erythrocytes by cold-vapor atomic absorption. Total mercury determined by urinalysis. Health complaints: at baseline, participants given 50-item symptom list and ranked three main complaints. Repeated for initially selected complaints at visits 1, 2, 6, 12, and 18 months after start of treatment. Number of complaints and total symptom score determined. At baseline and 6, 12, and 18 months after start of treatment: SF-36 (health-related QOL); Symptom Checklist SCL-90-R, (general index symptom severity overall psychological distress); KKG questionnaire (health-related locus of control). At baseline, two psychometric instruments: SAM questionnaire and FPI-R.	All randomised participants with baseline data on symptom score and dental status=ITT population. Statistical testing of main outcome measure was performed on intention-to-treat population, missing data replaced with baseline values by ANOVA. Sensitivity analyses performed for main outcome measure, with all available data or replacement of missing data by 'last value carried forward'. Exploratory analyses (without adjustment for multiple testing) for pre-defined secondary outcome measures. Descriptive statistics (mean values with standard deviations, 95% confidence intervals), and percentages provided. In case of baseline differences ($p<0.1$), ANCOVA with baseline values as covariates conducted. Additional sensitivity analyses were performed excluding participants who expressed a preference for specific treatment at baseline.
Weidenhammer 2009, [Germany]; JAP ⁶⁵	RCT (secondary data analysis – sample 1 and sample 2 historical records)	(a) Patient questionnaire “Symptom Check List SCL-90-R” providing a profile of nine primary symptom dimensions (somatisation, obsessive-compulsiveness, interpersonal sensitivity, depression, anxiety, hostility, phobic anxiety, paranoid ideation, psychoticism) and three global indices (global severity index, positive symptom distress index, positive symptom total); b) SAM questionnaire is a modified German version of the Self-Consciousness Scale to assess individual differences in the tendency to focus one’s attention on oneself. It includes two sub-scores for “private” and “public” self-consciousness with a total of 27 items; (c) documentation of symptoms and complaints - in sample 1, a 50-item-list was presented to the patients to estimate the intensity of symptoms by a 4 categories scale and in sample 2, the “SOMS” questionnaire was used. SOMS is a patient-	(a) Patient questionnaire “Symptom Check List SCL-90-R”: raw scores were transformed to a standard T-scale controlling for age and sex of the normal population. b) SAM questionnaire: simple group comparisons as well as adjustments concerning age, sex, and education. c) Documentation of symptoms and complaints. Fifteen matching symptoms from both questionnaires were selected for comparative analysis (supplemented by the symptom ‘metallic taste’). All questionnaires: descriptive analysis, chi squared tests; differences between groups in distributions of nominal-scaled variables; t tests for continuously distributed measures; analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) performed to adjust for covariates in the case of unequal sample structures.

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Methods	Analysis
		administered method to screen for somatoform disorders consisting of 53 different complaints.	
Weidenhammer 2010, [Germany]; JAP ⁶⁶	RCT (secondary data analysis)	At baseline and 12 months after onset, patients were given the following assessment instruments: a) a predefined symptom list with 50 items (scoring from 0 = not present to 3 = strong intensity) with a total symptom score (sum of all 50 item scores, range from 0 to 150); b) SF-36 to assess health-related quality of life (HRQoL); c) Symptom Checklist SCL-90-R, providing a general index of symptom severity as a measure for overall psychological distress; d) Mercury: total mercury in erythrocytes, inorganic mercury in blood plasma and mercury in urine (all in ng/ml) measured by cold-vapour atomic absorption. At baseline only: personality inventory FPI and self-reported duration of symptoms.	Comparisons between treatment groups were made using t-tests for independent samples and chi-squared tests for categorical data. Linear relationships were described using product-moment correlation coefficients. Stepwise regression analyses (with P < 0.05 for inclusion of predictors and tests for collinearity) were performed to identify predictors for continuous dependent variables (outcomes). Standardised weights of predictors indicate its relevance for the prediction of the outcome (ranging from -1 to +1).
Mikhailichenko 2019, (Taiwan); JAP ⁶⁷	Nested case-control	Longitudinal Health Insurance Database 2000 (LHID 2000): 1997–2013. ICD-9-CM codes used to identify disease diagnoses. Peer review improves reliability of diagnosis coding.	Categorical variables: numbers and percentages and compared using chi-squared or Fisher's exact test. Conditional logistic regression: crude and crude/adjusted ORs with 95% CI for case vs control group. Multivariate analysis: adjusted for co-variables that may have predisposed a patient to dementia. p<0.05= statistical significance.
Montebugnoli 2012, [Trinidad and Tobago]; JAP ⁶⁸	Before and after	Percutaneous patch tests by independent trained dermatologist: hypersensitivity to amalgam components and other metals (gold, palladium, nickel, chrome, potassium dichromate, cobalt, composite filling materials). All clinically healed patients had second biopsy 2 years after clinical disappearance of lesions in area adjacent to where first biopsy had shown a lichenoid reaction before amalgam replacement. A second biopsy also taken in 5 clinically unchanged patients who needed a second histologic examination as controls. Strict criteria were adopted to consider a lesion histologically healed.	Logistic regression analyses: identify clinical healing indicators for oral lesions. Fisher's exact test: identify indicators for histologic healing. Independent variables included gender, age (56 vs 56 years old), smoking habits, clinical features (white vs red lesions, and papular/reticular vs plaque vs atrophic vs ulcerative lesions), positivity to patch test, and direct contact or not with amalgams.
Naimi-Akbar 2013, [Sweden]; JAP ⁶⁹	Controlled before and after	Background information: collected from seven county councils, i.e. sex, DOB, number/date subsidised dental restoration replacement applications, whether application fully approved, approved with restriction/rejected. Postal questionnaire: restoration removal, self-rated health over time, symptoms and health-related quality of life (HRQoL). Outcomes: General symptoms, oral health, HRQoL, health over time.	Differences between exposure groups (replacement group/non-replacement group): distribution of oral and general health symptoms with chi-square test. HRQoL (MCS and PCS) mean scores compared and also compared with general population via two-sided t-test. Self-reported health changes over time with pair-wise comparisons: health status in year of application for subsidised restoration replacement compared with health status 1, 2 and 3 years afterwards. Differences between exposure groups with respect to proportions of subjects reporting improved, unchanged or deteriorated health status over time: chi-square test. Stratified analyses undertaken for subjects with

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Methods	Analysis
			approved applications only. In replacement group, only subjects who stated they had replaced dental amalgam fillings included in analyses. When comparing SF-12 scores with that of the general population, stratified analysis excluding study participants receiving disability pensions performed.
Perng 2023, [Taiwan]; JAP ⁷⁰	Retrospective cohort with control	LHID 2000 includes original claim data of one million people randomly sampled from 1997 registry for NHIRD beneficiaries. Caries determined by primary ICD-9 code: 521.0. Exposure to amalgam and composite resin identified through claim codes from 1997-2004. systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) identified by ICD-9 code: 710.0 and followed 2019 European League Against Rheumatism/American College of Rheumatology (EULAR/ACR) classification criteria for SLE ^{29,30} . To ensure validity: SLE diagnosed in at least 3 outpatient visits or at least 1 admission within 6 months from the first diagnosis.	Two-tailed t-test and chi-squared test: compare baseline characteristics between dental caries group vs non-dental caries group, and between group of exposure to different restorative materials. Cox proportional hazard models: hazard ratios (HRs) of SLE for patients with dental caries and with exposure to restorative materials, controlling covariates at baseline. Multiple Cox proportional hazard modelling: determined HRs of SLE for exposure to dental filling materials, while controlling baseline covariates. Kaplan–Meier survival curves and log-rank test: compared cumulative incidence of SLE. Relationship between degree dental caries and SLE: subgroup analyses based on the frequency of restorations, number of carious teeth, extracted severely carious teeth, and restorative materials throughout follow-up duration. Multivariable statistical model: to minimise confounders and to ensure effect of dental caries and effect of exposure to restorative materials on risk of SLE, adjustments made for age, sex, socioeconomic status, income, insured classification, co-morbidities, and frequency of dental visits. Covariate factors controlled included periodontitis, dental pulpitis, dental caries, carious tooth extraction, and carious teeth number from 1997 to 2004. Statistical significance: P-value <.05.
Pettini 2015, [Italy]; JAP ⁷¹	Cross sectional with control group	Blood samples: 2 replicate cultures for each sample. Cytogenetic tests: Culture time - 48 hour chromosomal aberrations and 72 hour for sister-chromatid exchange (in dark and 5 micogram/ml 5-bromodeoxyuridine)	Parametric Student's t-test: compare normally distributed variables. Non-parametric Mann-Whitney-test. Spearman's test: correlations between variables. Multiple regression: relationship between different variables. p<0.05=statistically significant.
Pezelj-Ribaric 2008, [Croatia]; JAP ⁷²	Controlled before and after	Demographic and health information: questionnaire. Oral lichenoid reactions (OLR) lesions: clinical examinations by two examiners. Described as either reticular or erosive/atrophic. Histopathological examination to confirm clinical diagnosis: specimens of OLR tissues obtained by taking a biopsy. Clinical diagnosis confirmed when a histological appearance included a band-like, mainly lymphocytic infiltrate in the connective tissue adjacent to the epithelial basement membrane, liquefaction degeneration of the basement membrane and destruction of the basal keratinocyte layer. Allergy: patch testing with all patients tested by experienced physician.	Demographic data: descriptive statistics (mean (SD)); ages analysed using one-way ANOVA. IL-6 and IL8 data: median and IQR and to assess differences: non-parametric Wilcoxon test for dependent samples and Mann-Whitney U-test for independent samples. Pearson's χ^2 test: analysis of histopathological features. Significance: p<0.005.

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Methods	Analysis
		<p>Tests: amalgam 5%, mercury ammonium chloride 1%, mercury 0.5%, thimerosal 0.1%, phenylmercuric borate 0.05%, phenylmercuric acetate 0.05%, and phenylmercuric nitrate 0.05% incorporated in petrolatum. Readings after 1, 2, 3 days. Saliva collection and cytokine assay: unstimulated saliva collected from participants between 9-11am using standard techniques. Final volume and flow rate determined gravimetrically. Repeated 3 months after amalgam replacement. Enzyme-linked Immunosorbent assay to determine salivary levels of IL-6 and IL-8. Test performed in duplicate and repeated 3 times. Amalgam replacement with composite resin, gold, porcelain or combination. After follow-up of between 2 months and 3.5 year, patients were evaluated in the clinic and OLR extent and severity graded.</p>	
Ptak 2023, [USA]; JAP ⁷³	Retrospective cohort	<p>Medical records: demographics, treatment, outcome variables. Two groups based on restorative treatment: non-crown or crown restorations. Pulpal disease = patients receiving additional treatment (initiation of endodontic therapy/extraction) on the same tooth by the time of data collection. Successful outcome = no additional treatment on restored tooth.</p>	<p>Descriptive statistics: frequency and % of endodontic treatments after placement of non-crown restorations. Chi square test: association between categoric independent variables and occurrence of pulpal disease (Fisher exact test when cell counts sparse). Logistic regression model: association between age and pulpal disease. Non-crown restorations: multivariate logistic regression model to assess association between restoration type and number of surfaces and occurrence of pulpal disease. Significance at $p \leq 0.05$.</p>
Rojas-Alcayaga 2012, [Chile]; JAP ⁷⁴	Cross sectional study with control group	<p>Patch testing: 25x10 Finn Chambers, including negative control (Vaseline) plus 20 allergens set. Patches placed on the upper back away from the midline. First reading at 48 hours and second at 72 hours. Evidence of sensitisation: erythema, infiltration (papular reaction), edema and/or vesicles. Intraoral clinical examination by two oral pathologists, both dental surgeons. Lesions documented photographically and diagnosis made by clinical and anatomopathological examination. Type and location of dental restorations or prosthetic devices registered.</p>	<p>Descriptive statistical analysis (proportions and mode). Chi-square tests (X²): association between atopic condition and sensitisation to dental materials. Significance: $p \leq 0.05$ (confidence interval 95%).</p>
Sundstrom 2010, [Sweden]; JAP ⁷⁵	Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group	<p>Health status assessed by self-reported health status questionnaire with 9 symptom composite scores: musculoskeletal, gastrointestinal, respiratory, cardiovascular, dermatological, neuropsychological, urination, visual, auditory. Cognitive status - 14 different cognitive tests with composite scores arranged into three composites: episodic memory, semantic memory and visuospatial ability.</p>	<p>Group differences in symptom profile: McNemar's test for categorical variables and paired t test for continuous variables; group differences in cognitive performance: examined with multivariate analyses of variance (MANOVA) by means of the General Linear Model; followed by univariate analyses of variance (ANOVA) with Bonferroni's correction. P-value significant at 0.05 except for MANOVA: 0.0167.</p>
Sundstrom 2011, [Sweden]; JAP ⁷⁶	Longitudinal and cross-sectional	<p>All participants examined at 2 sessions approximately 1 week apart. First test session with trained nurse: health examination/interview of health status and questionnaires regarding social variables/life events (Life Event</p>	<p>Demographic data was analysed by the McNemar's test, and continuous variables were compared using the paired t-test or Wilcoxon signed rank</p>

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Methods	Analysis
	with control group	Inventory) to complete between sessions. Health status: self-reported health status questionnaire.	test. All statistical tests were two-tailed with the critical P-value set at 0.05.
Suter 2016, [UK]; JAP ⁷⁷	Case control	Clinical audit of hospital records included by dental care provider; restorative material information from dental charting; skin patch tests and biopsy. Pathologist classified condition as: (i) oral lichen planus (OLP), (ii) oral lichenoid reactions (OLR) or (iii) consistent with either OLP or OLR. Demographic data, medical and smoking history, clinical characteristics including clinical presentation (reticular, plaque-like, erosive or mixed), unilateral, bilateral or widespread affliction, anatomic location and any available information on possible contact with restoration as recorded in the data entry were extracted. Restorative material and number of restorations present was transcribed from dental charting. Follow-up data were extracted from patients' clinic files. For those who were reviewed regularly, last follow-up was considered for analysis.	Testing between 3 patient groups. Compared affected sites, localisation/histopathological diagnosis of mucosal reactions and compared different groups of patients for improvement in OLR during follow up via Fisher's exact test. Compared gender, ethnicity, smoker status and type of mucosal reactions via Fisher-Freeman-Halton test. Compared age with one-way ANOVA. Cohens' Kappa measurements were performed between patients' subjective and clinician's assessment of improvement of OLR. No correction was applied for multiple testing Significance levels p<0.05.
Tadin 2014, [Croatia]; JAP ⁷⁸	RCT	Epithelial cell samples: swab technique gingival area; immediately before (control), and 7, 30 and 180 days following restoration. Each cell suspension processed separately: 1xDNA damage using comet assay, 1 analysed by micronucleus assay in gingival epithelial cells.	Descriptive statistics: mean, standard error, standard deviation, and relative standard deviation, median and minimum and maximum values. ANOVA and Student–Newman–Keuls tests: existence/absence of statistically significant differences between median values for each scored cytogenetic endpoints (micronucleus, binucleated cell, karyorrhexis, karyolysis, nuclear bud and “broken eggs,” tail length, % DNA). Multiple regression: impact of predictor variables (demographic, lifestyle, personal factors, and dietary aspects) to a specific cytogenetic endpoint. Significance level: 0.05.
Tseng 2020a [MS], [Taiwan]; JAP ⁷⁹	Case control	Longitudinal dataset; disease diagnoses defined according to ICD-9-CM, AMF cases by treatment codes (89001C, 89002C, 89003C, 89101C, 89102C, and 89103C).	Chi squared test, multivariate logistic regression; Adjustments were made for confounders- age, sex, income, region, and Charlson comorbidity index (CCI).
Tseng 2020b [ET], [Taiwan]; JAP ⁸⁰	Case control	Longitudinal dataset; disease diagnoses defined according to ICD-9-CM, AMF cases by treatment codes (89001C, 89002C, 89003C, 89101C, 89102C, and 89103C).	Chi squared test, multivariate logistic regression; Adjustments were made for confounders- age, sex, income, region, and Charlson comorbidity index (CCI).
Watson 2011, [Republic of Seychelles]; JAP ⁸¹	Prospective longitudinal cohort study	Prenatal Hg0 exposure - primary metric: total number of amalgam surfaces present in the mother during gestation. A secondary exposure metric using an occlusal point score for occlusal surfaces of amalgams on premolars and molars (score of 1= small size occlusal amalgams; 2= medium size; 3= large size occlusal amalgams) was used. Collected 10 years after birth of child through a dental clinical examination and retrospective abstraction of	Prenatal Hg0 exposure and prenatal MeHg in relation to the six outcomes - modelling, regression model. Associations between each of the six outcomes and prenatal Hg0 exposure examined using 4 estimations of Hg0 exposure: n of amalgam surfaces using Lower Exposure Limit (LEL), amalgam surfaces using Upper Exposure Limit (UEL), occlusal point score using LEL, occlusal point score using UEL.

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Methods	Analysis
		<p>mother's dental records (placement and disposition of amalgam restorations) by dental personnel. Amalgams known to have been initially placed after the birth of the child were excluded. Prenatal MeHg - assessing the concentration of total mercury (THg) in a segment of maternal hair growing during gestation. Outcomes: at age 66 months children assessed on overall intelligence [General Cognitive Index (GCI) of the McCarthy Scales of Children's Abilities (MSCA)], expressive and receptive language ability [Preschool Language Scale (PLS) Total Score], reading and arithmetic achievement [Letter Word Recognition and Applied Problems subtests of the Woodcock-Johnson (W-J) Tests of Achievement], drawing and copying to measure visual-spatial ability (Bender Gestalt test using the Koppitz scoring protocol), and the child's social and adaptive behavior [Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL)].</p>	<p>Models fit with and without adjustment for prenatal and recent postnatal MeHg exposure metrics. Significance at $p =$ smaller or equal to 0.05.</p>
<p>Watson 2012, [Republic of Seychelles]; JAP⁸²</p>	<p>Prospective longitudinal cohort study</p>	<p>Prenatal Hg0 exposure from amalgams: the total number of amalgam surfaces present in the mother during gestation by examining the mothers shortly before or just after the birth of her child, and reviewing the historic dental records maintained by the national dental service. Secondary exposure metric using an occlusal point score (1= small size occlusal amalgams, 2= medium size, 3= large size occlusal) was used.</p>	<p>Prenatal Hg0 exposure and prenatal MeHg in relation to outcomes - linear regression model: relationship between amalgam surfaces and mental (MDI) and psychomotor (PDI) developmental indices of the Bayley Scales at 9 and 30 months. Models with and without adjustment for prenatal MeHg, n-3 and n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) and sex. Secondary analysis: model with amalgam replaced by occlusal points. In all regression models covariates were sex, family status at 9 months (0 if living with both parents, 1 if not), maternal age at birth, birth weight, maternal intelligence [assessed by the Matrices subtest of the Kaufman Brief Intelligence Test (K-BIT)], socioeconomic status (SES) (measured by the Hollingshead Four-Factor SES), and the Pediatric Review of Children's Environmental Support and Stimulation (PROCESS). All continuous variables except sex/family status. Two-tailed p-value of <0.05 for significance.</p>
<p>Watson 2013, [Republic of Seychelles]; JAP⁸³</p>	<p>Prospective longitudinal cohort study</p>	<p>Prenatal Hg0 exposure - Primary metric was the total number of amalgam surfaces present in the mother during gestation. A secondary exposure metric was an occlusal point score. The children's test battery included: finger tapping [(FT) dominant and non-dominant hands]; three subtests of the Preschool Language Scale-Revised Edition [Total Language Score (PLS-TL), Verbal Ability Score (PLS-VA), and Auditory Comprehension (PLS-AC)]; two subtests of the Woodcock-Johnson Scholastic Achievement Test, second edition (LetterWord Identification and Applied Problems); and two subtests of the Kaufman Brief Intelligence Test [Verbal Knowledge (KBIT-VK) and Matrices (KBIT-M)]. Mothers completed the Child Behavior Checklist</p>	<p>Linear regression models: covariates known or predicted to influence neurodevelopmental outcomes, included sex, child age, family status at 5 years (1 if living with both parents, 0 if not), maternal age, birth weight, maternal intelligence (assessed by KBIT-M), socioeconomic status (SES) (measured by the Hollingshead Four-Factor SES), and the Pediatric Review of Children's Environmental Support and Stimulation (PROCESS).</p>

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Methods	Analysis
		(CBCL), the Kaufman Brief Intelligence Test [Matrices (KBIT-M)], and the Pediatric Review of Children's Environmental Support and Stimulation (PROCESS). Tests were available in English and Seychellois Creole, and the preferred version was administered by an experienced team of trained maternal and child health nurses.	
Weber 2012, [USA]; JAP ⁸⁴	Prospective longitudinal with control	General medical and dental histories of the patients were reviewed, and relevant physical examination findings were recorded. For each patient with oral squamous cell carcinoma (SCC), patch testing with 28 metal allergens and control patch testing with 8 metal allergens was carried out. Patch test results were based on identification of erythema and induration, with only 1 and or greater reactions considered positive. Timeframe: allergens were left in place for 48 hours, and the reactions were read initially on day 2 ± 24 hours and then again on day 5 ± 24 hours, day 7 ± 24 hours, and day 14 ± 24 hours (reading stopped at day 5, 1 year into study).	Oral SCC cases: % of patients with allergy was reported, along with the 95% confidence interval (CI) for each of the 28 allergens calculated by the exact binomial method. The relative risk of oral SCC due to metal contact allergy was estimated by calculating the odds ratio (OR). Confounders were not reported.
Wright 2012, [UK]; JAP ⁸⁵	Case control	Mercury level: urine samples collected and analysed at Health and Safety Laboratory in Sheffield by Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS). Number of amalgam fillings: dental records. ASD: diagnoses of Childhood Autism, Atypical Autism or Asperger Syndrome were made using Research Diagnostic Criteria (RDC) from the World Health Organisation International Classification of Diseases system version 10 through a multidisciplinary panel that considered all local ASD assessments. Where there was uncertainty, the Autism Diagnostic Inventory-Revised (ADI-R) and the Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule-Generic (ADOS-G) were used to support ICD-10 diagnosis.	Relationship between mercury levels and diagnostic group: test was performed twice: i) without creatinine correction and ii) with creatinine correction. Creatinine ratios were calculated to correct for variations in urinary mercury caused by body mass and urine concentration. Multiple regression to adjust for the effects of age, gender and number of fillings; 4 groups compared using Kruskal Wallis tests for continuous data and Chi-Square for categorical data; Kruskal-Wallis tests utilised due to skew in the raw data. p-value of <0.05 was considered to indicate statistical significance.
Zwicker 2014, [Canada]; JAP ⁸⁶	Retrospective cohort study	Dentist measured data on amalgam surfaces through x-rays and visual inspection. Mercury levels: urine samples from participants, creatinine measured by modified Jaffe method and elemental testing measured using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). Self-reported physical and mental health symptoms on a scale of 1 to 10. The 14 symptoms reported were: headaches or migraines; memory loss; depression; fatigue or sleep disturbance; anxiety; being unusually moody; confusion; stomach problems; experiencing loss of sense of smell or taste; shakiness in hands; paraesthesia; unintentionally dropping things; coordination problems and muscle weakness.	Urine mercury levels: non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis equality-of-populations rank test with Dunn's multiple comparison post hoc test and Bonferroni correction; box plots to show the distribution of mercury across groups. Wilcoxon signed-rank test for intergroup comparison or comparison of two related measures in the treatment and positive amalgam groups. Symptom deterioration: self-reported using an ordinal scale, odds ratio of symptom improvement using logistic regression models (controlling for age and sex). Descriptive statistics to summarise variables: means and standard deviations (SD) for continuous variables, % for binary or categorical variables.

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